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Nutritional Modeling and Energy Metabolism in Poultry Nutrition

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Preface

Proceedings of the **"Symposium in Nutritional Modeling and Energy Metabolism in Poultry Nutrition"**

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The international scientific symposium, **"Nutritional Modeling and Energy Metabolism in Poultry Nutrition,"** is scheduled for **Jun 02-03, 2026, at São Paulo State University (UNESP), Jaboticabal, SP, Brazil.**

The objective of this symposium is to discuss modelling and net energy systems and show the tools developed at UNESP-Jaboticabal. The scientific foundation for this symposium is derived from research conducted at Lavinesp – Jaboticabal, São Paulo State University, over 25 years, with financial support from the FAPESP-funded five thematic projects (Fapesp Proc. Proc. 97/00671-8, 2008/5055-3, 2013/25761-4, 2019/01853-3, and 2019/26575-6). These research projects provide tools for application in poultry production and address critical gaps in novel net-energy systems, facilitating their practical implementation in poultry production. The focus is on advancing the adoption of the net energy system and the application of modeling approaches.

The event shows the results and introduces model-based tools from these research projects designed to enhance the feasibility and precision of practical feed formulation, thereby optimizing production efficiency and sustainability.

To promote a global-level discussion, the symposium convenes a distinguished panel of internationally recognized scientists and industry professionals. These experts present relevant topics, fostering high-level knowledge exchange and practical insights.

Additionally, the symposium is designed to serve as a space to discuss net energy systems and to promote the use of simulation modeling as a cornerstone for strategic decision-making in poultry nutrition. The event is strategically directed towards poultry nutritionists, industry professionals, academics, and researchers working in applied poultry science. By bringing together these key stakeholders, the symposium aims to stimulate critical discussion, bridge the gap between research and application, and advance the field by addressing contemporary topics in poultry science.

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1. Net energy in feed for broiler chickens

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Abstract

Net energy (NE) in poultry is considered a more precise energy system compared to conventional apparent metabolizable energy (AME) and its correction by nitrogen balance (AMEn) due to its ability to consider the energy lost as heat increment from nutrient metabolism that averages 25% of AMEn and is variable with feed characteristics. However, unlike pigs, NE is not yet implemented in poultry nutrition. This study aimed to develop predictive equations for NE value and evaluate available equations in the literature, applying them to complete feeds and individual feedstuffs. A total of 48 diets with wide variability in their chemical composition (28 to 44% for starch; 18 to 29% for crude protein (CP), and 5.6 to 12% for fat (EE)). To obtain wide variability, traditional and non-traditional ingredients were used for feed formulation (wheat, corn, poultry byproduct meal, peanut meal, meat and bone meal, soybean meal, cottonseed meal, canola meal, wheat brand, rice brand, millet, sorghum, starch, poultry fat, and soybean oil). Each diet was randomly assigned to chambers within each batch and tested in 4 replicates. Equations were developed using stepwise multiple regression to assess the significance of potential predictors. Additional NE equations from Tay-Zar et al. (2024) and Wu et al. (2019) were evaluated using the error decomposition procedure. This procedure was conducted on a dataset collected from the literature, in which AME and NE were measured for complete diets and for individual, more common raw materials for broiler chickens and laying hens. diet

AMEn (3266 kcal/kg dry matter on average; range: 2840 to 3671) and AMEn/GE (71.4% on average) was as expected. The NE/AMEn ratio averaged 75.8% (range: 70.0 to 80.2%) and increased with EE and decreased with CP in the feed. The NE equations ($NE \text{ (kcal/kg DM)} = 0.815 \times AME - 12.8 \times CP + 4.76 \times EE$). In the equation comparisons, it was observed that $NE = 0.815 \times AME - 12.8 \times CP + 4.76 \times EE$ presented a lower error (RMSE=92 kcal/kg, 4.3%), followed by equation $NE = 0.815 \times AME - 12.8 \times CP + 4.76 \times EE$ (RMSE=104 kcal/kg, 4.5%). However, the second model identified distribution as the principal source of error (80.2%), which was validated as a more powerful model for complete feeds. In the evaluation of individual feedstuffs (cottonseed, corn, SBM, wheat grain, and wheat brand), $NE = 0.815 \times AME - 6.22 \times CP + 4.78 \times EE - 5.74 \times NDF$ presented a lower error (239 kcal/kg, 13.4%) with desirable error of distribution as the main source of error. In conclusion, NE equations are a powerful tool for predicting energy values for complete feeds and individual feedstuffs.

Keywords: energy utilization, feedstuff, feeds, chemical composition.

Introduction

Energy is one of the main components in feed that influences feed cost and feed intake regulation and is a strategic component for developing optimization strategies. For that, the energy system implemented in feed formulation should be more accurate and account for all energy losses during animal utilization. In this context, net energy (NE) emerged as a viable alternative for optimizing feed formulation (Carre et al., 2014; Noblet et al., 2025).

Apparent metabolizable energy (AME) system and its nitrogen-corrected expression (AMEn) are predominantly used in poultry diet formulation. Even though these systems work well in traditional corn-soybean meal diets, they can fail when alternative ingredients are included (e.g., wheat, sorghum, canola meal, DDG), which can alter the nutritional composition and, consequently, energy utilization (Swick et al., 2013).

Determination of the heat increment in complete diets can provide valuable information for nutritionists formulating diets that optimize energy utilization. Currently, some NE equations have been proposed (Wu et al., 2019; Tay-Zar et al., 2024) based on feed chemical composition, but their applicability to individual raw materials remains unclear. This study aimed to develop predictive equations for NE value and evaluate available equations in the literature, applying them to complete feeds and individual feedstuffs.

Methodology

A total of 1536 male Cobb 500 broiler chickens at 21 days old were randomly allocated to 48 experimental diets. The diets were formulated aiming for a wide variation in their AMEn and chemical composition (Table 1). Each experimental diet was analyzed for its chemical composition. The diets were fed to bird kept in open-circuit respiratory chambers from 21 to 28 days of age (8 birds per cage), with four repetitions per experimental diets.

Table 1. Variation in energy and nutritional composition of 48 diets formulated to develop NE equations for broiler chickens.

Variable	Analyzed		
	Max	Min	Avg.
Crude protein, %	29.1	18	22.86
Ether extract, %	12.3	5.6	9.16
Starch, %	44.4	27.5	38.53
NDF, %	20.6	8.1	13.68
Organic matter, %	93.9	91.9	92.98
GE	4798	4416	4600
AME	3884	3023	3459
AMEn	3671	2840	3266
NE	3065	2260	2624
AME/GE	83.4	68.8	76
AMEn/GE	78.7	64.3	71.4
NE/AMEn	80.2	70	75.8
NE/AME	83.7	75.7	80.2

The experimental trial consists of pre-experimental (1-14-day-old), diet-adaptation (15-20-day-old), and experimental (21-28-day-old) periods. At 21 days old, the birds were

transferred to respirometric chambers composed of an open-circuit indirect calorimetry system.

In respirometric chambers, oxygen consumption and CO₂ production are used to calculate heat production. Additionally, during the same period, total excreta collection methods were performed to determine the AME and AMEn.

Using overall data, a stepwise multiple regression method was performed to develop the NE prediction equation, with AME, AMEn, crude protein, ether extract, starch, ash, etc. as predictors.

For the NE equation evaluation, two datasets were constructed with information in the literature: 1. NE were determined for complete diets, and 2. NE determination by the substitution method for individual ingredients used in poultry. The dataset 1 consisted of 156 values of chemical composition and NE values conducted in broiler chickens and laying hens, and the dataset 2 consisted of 51 NE-determined values for feedstuffs used in broiler chickens and laying hens (corn, cottonseed meal, soybean meal, wheat brand, wheat grain, DDGs, citrus pulp, and palm kernel meal). For each piece of information, the NE equations published by Wu et al. (2019), Tay-Zar et al. (2024), and the equations developed here were applied, and error calculations and decomposition analyses were performed. The root mean square error (RMSE) was calculated and expressed in percentage, and the decomposition of error was divided into error due to central tendency (ECT), error of regression (ER), and error of distribution (ED) to evaluate the feasibility of each equation in complete diets and individual raw materials.

NE equation development

Experimental diets showed adequate variation in their energy and nutritional composition to proceed with equation development: AMEn (3266 kcal/kg dry matter on average; range: 2840 to 3671) and AMEn/GE (71.4% on average) were as expected.

The NE/AMEn ratio averaged 75.8% (range: 70.0 to 80.2%) and increased with EE and decreased with CP in the feed.

Based on the dataset of 48 measurements of NE, AME, and AMEn and their respective chemical composition, two equations were developed for broiler chickens:

$$\text{NE (kcal/kg DM)} = 0.815 \times \text{AMEn} - 12.8 \times \text{CP} + 14.76 \times \text{EE}$$

$$\text{NE (kcal/kg DM)} = 0.820 \times \text{AME} - 10.04 \times \text{CP} + 14.81 \times \text{EE}$$

Due to high positive correlation with AME and AMEn, and the ether extract, and also with the negative correlation with CP due to high heat contribution of this nutrient to the heat increment, these components presented high potential to compose predictors of the NE equations. The equation's structure was similar to that proposed by Wu et al. (2019) but differed in the coefficient for CP.

NE equations evaluation

In general, NE equations showed similar predictors, with differences in their coefficients. Additionally, during model evaluation, the equations presented here and those proposed by Wu et al. (2019) provided more data due to their practicality for determining AME, AMEn, and NE (n=76). Equations proposed by Tay-Zar et al. (2024) included predictors such as CF, ADF, and NDF, which, in many studies (n=59), are not included, limiting their wide applicability.

For complete diets (Table 2 and Figure 1), equation comparisons showed that $\text{NE} = 0.815 \times \text{AME} - 12.8 \times \text{CP} + 14.76 \times \text{EE}$ had the lower error (RMSE=92 kcal/kg, 4.3%), followed by $\text{NE} = 0.815 \times \text{AME} - 12.8 \times \text{CP} + 14.76 \times \text{EE}$ (RMSE=104 kcal/kg, 4.5%).

However, the second model identified distribution as the principal source of error (80.2%), which was validated as a more powerful model for complete feeds.

Figure 1. Predicted-observed NE value of 1598 individual observations in the literature, which was applied to the evaluation of the NE equation of Riveros et al (under review), Tay-Zar et al (2024), and Wu et al (2019).

Equations evaluations for individual feedstuffs (cottonseed, corn, SBM, wheat grain, and wheat brand) are presented in Table 3 and Figure 2.

Table 2. NE equations evaluation for complete diets for poultry by error decomposition analyses.

Sources	Equation	n	RMSE	RMSE, %	ECT, %	ER, %	ED, %
Riveros et al.	$0.815 \cdot \text{AME} - 12.8 \cdot \text{CP} + 14.76 \cdot \text{EE}$	76	104	4.5	3.1	16.7	80.2
	$0.820 \cdot \text{AMEn} - 10.04 \cdot \text{CP} + 14.81 \cdot \text{EE}$	74	223	9.6	15.6	19.3	65.1
Tay-Zar et al.	$0.811 \cdot \text{AME} - 6.220 \cdot \text{CP} + 4.780 \cdot \text{EE} - 11.720 \cdot \text{CF}$	59	116	5.1	61.4	8.5	30.1
	$0.809 \cdot \text{AME} - 5.500 \cdot \text{CP} + 2.870 \cdot \text{EE} - 9.569 \cdot \text{ADF}$	28	92	4.3	56.7	0.8	42.4
	$0.815 \cdot \text{AME} - 6.220 \cdot \text{CP} + 4.780 \cdot \text{EE} - 5.740 \cdot \text{NDF}$	40	157	7.2	50	17.3	32.8
Wu et al.	$0.781 \cdot \text{AME} - 6.698 \cdot \text{CP} + 6.938 \cdot \text{EE}$	76	108	4.7	17.4	6.9	75.6
	$0.808 \cdot \text{AMEn} - 4.067 \cdot \text{CP} + 7.416 \cdot \text{EE}$	74	283	12.2	41.8	14.5	43.6

It was evidenced that the equation $NE=0.815 \times AME - 6.22 \times CP + 4.78 \times EE - 5.74 \times NDF$ presented a lower error (239 kcal/kg, 13.4%) with distribution error as the main source of error, suggesting that.

Figure 2. Observed-predicted NE value of 51 data of different feedstuffs used in broiler chickens, evaluating the NE equation of Riveros et al (under review), Tay-Zar et al (2024), and Wu et al (2019).

Equations evaluations for individual feedstuffs (cottonseed, corn, SBM, wheat grain, and wheat brand) are presented in Table 3 and Figure 2. It was evidenced that the equation $NE=0.815 \times AME - 6.22 \times CP + 4.78 \times EE - 5.74 \times NDF$ presented a lower error (239 kcal/kg, 13.4%) with distribution error as the main source of error, suggesting that depending on the characteristic of the ingredients, can feasible their application in individual feedstuffs.

Table 3. NE equations evaluation for individual ingredients for poultry by error decomposition analysis.

Sources	Equation	n	RMSE	RMSE, %	ECT, %	ER, %	ED, %
Riveros et al.	$0.815 \cdot \text{AME} - 12.8 \cdot \text{CP} + 14.76 \cdot \text{EE}$	50	320	15.7	8.4	41.2	50.4
	$0.820 \cdot \text{AMEn} - 10.04 \cdot \text{CP} + 14.81 \cdot \text{EE}$	42	377	18.8	8.2	55.2	36.7
Tay-Zar et al.	$0.811 \cdot \text{AME} - 6.220 \cdot \text{CP} + 4.780 \cdot \text{EE} - 11.720 \cdot \text{CF}$	36	335	15.3	32.3	26.9	40.8
	$0.809 \cdot \text{AME} - 5.500 \cdot \text{CP} + 2.870 \cdot \text{EE} - 9.569 \cdot \text{ADF}$	27	251	13.9	26.5	7.7	65.8
	$0.815 \cdot \text{AME} - 6.220 \cdot \text{CP} + 4.780 \cdot \text{EE} - 5.740 \cdot \text{NDF}$	27	239	13.4	11.4	4.8	83.8
Wu et al.	$0.781 \cdot \text{AME} - 6.698 \cdot \text{CP} + 6.938 \cdot \text{EE}$	50	298	14.6	27.1	14.2	58.7
	$0.808 \cdot \text{AMEn} - 4.067 \cdot \text{CP} + 7.416 \cdot \text{EE}$	42	382	19	39.1	26.2	34.7

Practical application

Based on the results, the NE equation can be applied to complete diets and individual ingredients. The application of the NE equation in practical feed formulation is a powerful tool for identifying the efficiency of raw material utilization and the possibility of substitutions (e.g., reduced dependence on corn and SBM) with alternative ingredients (Table 4 and Figure 3). Additionally, implementing the NE system in poultry formulation can represent an opportunity to optimize diets.

Figure 3. Representation of the variability of the NE value observed and predicted in feedstuffs for poultry.

The NE system in poultry can determine the energy available for growth and production. It can be applied for broiler chickens and laying hens, expressing a different scale (Table 4).

Table 4. Determined and predicted NE value of feedstuff in broiler chickens and laying hens.

Feedstuff	AME (kcal/kg)		AMEn (kcal/kg)		NE observed (kcal/kg)		NE predicted (kcal/kg)		NE:AME	NE:AMEn
Broiler chickens										
Cottonseed	2392	± 303	2044	± 285	1426	± 324	1263	± 247	0.6	0.70
Corn	4091	± 124	4084	± 121	2679	± 212	3241	± 99	0.65	0.66
SBM	2726	± 255	2348	± 243	1657	± 200	1592	± 238	0.61	0.71
Wheat grain	3164	± 76	3102	± 76	2459	± 173	2405	± 63	0.78	0.79
Wheat brand	1700	± 84	1652	± 80	1212	± 50	1181	± 69	0.71	0.73
Laying hens										
Cottonseed	2909	± 127	2691	± 145	1707	± 233	1624	± 118	0.59	0.63
Corn	3529	± 99	3501	± 72	2549	± 206	2783	± 75	0.72	0.73
SBM	2538		2543		1678		1500		0.66	0.66
Wheat brand	1975	± 234	1916	± 260	1490	± 495	1406	± 185	0.75	0.78
DDGS	3110		2790		1800		2230		0.58	0.65
Fermented citrus pulp	2094		2058		1228		1518		0.59	0.6

Conclusion

In conclusion, NE equations are a powerful tool for predicting energy values for complete feeds and individual feedstuffs, and their selection should consider practicality and applicability.

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2. Net energy evaluation in feedstuffs for laying hens: and comparative evaluation

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Introduction

An efficient diet formulation must follow the dynamic way in which birds utilize nutrients throughout the production cycle. In this context, tools that accurately estimate the energy value of ingredients are necessary, especially because this nutrient accounts for about 60% of feed costs. Traditionally, metabolizable energy (ME) has been used as the basis for formulation due to its simplicity and consistency. However, this system has important limitations, as it does not account for energy losses in the form of heat increment during nutrient metabolism (Noblet et al., 2024).

In this scenario, net energy (NE) stands out, as it represents the fraction of energy available for maintenance, body deposition, and egg production, incorporating losses associated with the heat increment (Barzegar et al., 2019). Considering that modern birds are highly efficient and continuously adjust their energy use, NE provides a more accurate representation of how ingredients are truly utilized. Thus, more than a conceptual improvement, it is a practical approach capable of increasing formulation precision, reducing costs, and expanding the use of non-conventional ingredients in animal feeding.

Methodology

To enable the practical application of this concept, NE prediction equations were developed based on the nutritional composition of different diets. The study was conducted at Lavinesp (Unesp/FCAV), using 288 Hy-Line W80 laying hens. From 19 weeks of age, birds were housed in a controlled experimental facility, assigned to a completely randomized design, and fed 32 experimental diets. These diets were formulated to provide wide variation in chemical composition and energy levels. This variability was intentional, allowing the development of robust models with low multicollinearity among variables. There was substantial variation in metabolizable energy, crude protein, ether extract, fiber, and starch, covering a wide range of nutritional scenarios commonly observed in commercial laying operations.

NE was measured using respirometric chambers, which allowed precise determination of heat production under both fed and fasting conditions. From these measurements, the birds' energy balance was calculated, including metabolizable energy intake, total heat production, and energy retained in the body and eggs. These data supported the development of multiple regression models using diet composition as predictor variables. Among the equations obtained, one showed high predictive capacity and practical applicability, expressed as:

$$NE = 0.765 \times AME - 8.95 \times CP + 18.24 \times EE$$

This equation objectively summarizes the contribution of the main energy-yielding nutrients, incorporating both the dietary energy base (ME) and the specific effects of protein and fat on net energy.

The practical application of this model provides important insights for feed formulation. First, it becomes clear that ME alone does not adequately describe the true energy value of ingredients. Protein, for example, is associated with a reduction in available NE due to its higher heat increment, whereas ether extract positively contributes to NE because of its higher utilization efficiency. This behavior highlights

that nutrients are used differently by the animal, something not captured by the traditional ME system. In practice, this means that ingredients with high protein tend to have their energy value overestimated, while fat ingredients are often underestimated when evaluated on an ME basis.

This adjustment in how ingredient energy is evaluated has direct implications for ingredient selection. Ingredients should not be assessed only by their ME content, but also by their efficiency of conversion into net energy. As illustrated in Table 1 corn grain with 6.92% CP shows 0.27% higher efficiency than corn high-lysine, even though this last one has higher ME and CP levels.

Table 1. Energetic determination of the principal feedstuff based on their energy and nutritional composition.

Ingredient	ME	CP	EE	NE	k
Corn Gluten Feed 21% CP	1880	21.00	3.20	1309	69.61
Corn DDGS	2410	30.50	6.79	1695	70.31
Corn DDG-HP	3060	42.10	11.90	2181	71.28
Corn Germ	3144	10.30	10.10	2497	79.43
Corn Grain 6.92% CP	3264	6.92	3.50	2499	76.56
Corn Grain 7.65% CP	3296	7.65	3.65	2520	76.44
Corn Grain 7.86% CP	3364	7.86	3.81	2573	76.47
Corn Grain High Lysine	3405	8.26	3.66	2598	76.29
Corn Pre-cooked	3429	7.94	1.64	2582	75.30
Corn Grain 8.80% CP	3464	8.80	4.08	2646	76.37
Corn Grain High Oil	3560	8.21	6.30	2765	77.66
Corn Gluten Meal 60% CP	3705	61.50	1.98	2320	62.62
Average					74.03
Ingredient	ME	CP	EE	NE	k
Soybean Hulls	841	14.4	3.01	569	67.70
Soybean Meal 44% CP	2120	44.4	1.05	1244	58.66
Soybean Meal 45% CP	2258	45.4	1.95	1357	60.08
Soybean Meal 48% CP	2295	48.1	1.83	1359	59.20
Soybean Meal 46% CP	2396	46.5	2.85	1469	61.30
Soybean Protein Conc.	2635	62.7	0.47	1463	55.53
Soybean Part-defat. Tost.	2726	40.2	10.5	1917	70.33
Soybean Part-defat. Extr.	2811	40.2	10.5	1982	70.51
Soybean Full-Fat Toasted	3240	37.3	18.8	2488	76.78
Soybean Full-Fat Extruded	3393	37.3	18.8	2605	76.77
Soybean Full-Fat Micronized	3652	39.7	20.8	2818	77.16
Average					66.73

Similarly, soybean meal 45% CP, widely used in Brazil, is about 1.22% less efficient than soybean meal 46% CP, which also has higher ME and protein levels. These examples demonstrate that the NE/ME ratio should be incorporated as a key criterion in ingredient evaluation. Therefore, energy efficiency becomes an additional tool to support more precise nutritional decisions.

Figure 1. Comparative energy and efficiency of evaluation of principal feedstuff used in feed formulation.

Furthermore, when considering energy conversion efficiency, several non-conventional ingredients show competitive performance (Figure 1). By-products such

as rice bran, bakery waste, citrus pulp, and cassava can present high energy efficiency, making them economically attractive options. On the other hand, high-protein ingredients, such as animal by-product meals or protein concentrates, tend to show lower energy efficiency, which should be taken into account during formulation.

Another important aspect is the environmental impact. NE-based formulation promotes the reduction of CP levels in the diet, since excess protein is energetically penalized. This strategy allows greater use of synthetic amino acids, reducing costs and improving nitrogen utilization efficiency. Consequently, lower CP levels in diets lead to reduced nitrogen excretion by birds, contributing to lower emissions of nitrogen compounds and meeting current demands for more sustainable production systems.

Conclusion

In summary, the use of NE prediction models represents a practical and efficient tool for laying hens nutrition. By accounting for differences in nutrient metabolic utilization, this system enables more accurate ingredient evaluation and opens new opportunities in feed formulation. The transition from ME to NE should not be seen merely as a theoretical change, but as an applied strategy to improve productive efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance sustainability in poultry production.

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3. Energy Requirements and Utilization: Principles and Methodologies

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Introduction

In most monogastric species, feed accounts for the largest proportion of the production costs and among these costs, energy is one of the main factors determining feed price. Associated with this, a tailored formulation of diet is required to balance each component of the formula with each other and to balance the whole diet with nutrient requirements of animals. Nevertheless, this needs an accurate estimation of animal energy requirements and how animals use energy, as not all the gross energy (i.e. the energy measured as heat of combustion of the diet) is available for metabolic purposes. Measuring the excretion of energy in the feces, urine and as gases from fermentation in the digestive tract allows for the calculation of the so-called metabolizable energy (ME), which is the energy available for metabolic pathways. The latter are not 100% efficient, resulting in other losses of energy as heat production (HP). Apart from the direct measurement of HP no longer in use for livestock species, indirect calculation of HP from respiratory gas exchanges (Brouwer, 1965) has been widely used to measure both energy requirements and energy utilization. Energy requirements are generally defined according to the factorial approach as the sum of maintenance requirements, production requirements (as growth, eggs, milk, ...) and other requirements as those associated with physical activity, thermoregulation or health. All these requirements result in a cumulative HP of which the components have to be partitioned to be able to identify the single

contributors to total requirements. In producing animals, it is especially difficult to partition the use of energy between what is due to maintenance and what is due to production as all involved metabolic pathways occur at the same time. Additionally, long term metabolic adaptation may depend on the level of production, reinforcing the vagueness of the border between maintenance and production. For instance, muscle protein turnover can be viewed as the maintenance of muscle mass, but its rate can be modified with level of protein deposition and growth (Sarri et al., 2024) suggesting that at least a part if not all the associated energy cost should be considered in the production needs. The last decades and the increasing development of kinetic measurements, mathematical computing and modelling approaches have renewed the classical picture of energy utilization in producing animals, allowing for an evolution of scientific concepts reflecting energy metabolism and principles of animal feeding.

Indirect calorimetry generally refers to methods allowing for an indirect determination of HP. Apart from the comparative slaughter technique or isotope infusion and recovery for the estimation of HP on a long term basis and for instance in free ranging animals, the method based on respiratory gas exchange measurements has been widely used since the 18th century (Lavoisier, 1780). It is based on the assumption of stoichiometric relationships between O₂, CO₂ and heat in the equations of nutrient oxidation (Brouwer, 1965), considering that all biological pathways can be resume as simple stoichiometric equations irrespective of intermediary steps (Gerrits et al., 2015). It requires the measurement of O₂ consumption and CO₂ production by the animals. If measurements over a short period of time can be achieved thanks face mask or hood (Maia et al., 2014), prolonged measurements require the housing of animals in a box called respiration chamber and gas exchanges are then measured from the change in their concentrations in the air in ("closed circuit") or flowing out of ("open circuit") the box. In open-circuit systems, high frequency measurements allow for the detailed description of the dynamics of HP and thus energy metabolism over very short periods (Kuhla et al., 2015) but proper conditions of measurements (mixing of air

in the chamber, minimal leakages, accuracy of sensors) are mandatory to prevent from inaccuracy in the estimates (Heetkamp et al., 2015). Together with mathematical modelling and computation, high frequency measurements of gas exchanges are used to link the variations of HP to events occurring in the respiration chamber (feed intake, physical activity) to partition HP between thermic effect of feeding (TEF), physical activity related HP (AHP) and basal metabolism estimated as the fasting heat production (FHP; van Milgen et al., 1997; Figure 1). The latter is calculated as the horizontal asymptotic value towards which the decreasing HP strives during a 24-h period of fasting and is considered to quantify the maintenance energy requirements. When FHP is subtracted from HP, heat increment is calculated as the inefficiency of using ME for net energy (NE).

Figure 1. Example of heat production partitioning between components due to basal metabolic rate (fasting heat production, FHP), physical activity (AHP) and thermic effect of feeding (TEF) in growing pig.

The partitioning of HP between components has been used in various species (Labussière et al., 2015) and one of the major findings was the determination of the best coefficient to calculate the metabolic body weight which is a standardizing unit to express all data of energy metabolism. For instance in growing broilers, the 0.70 coefficient has been estimated as a better coefficient than the conventional value of

0.75 used for mature animals (Noblet et al., 2015), as it allows for a better description of the growth of metabolically active organs relative to body weight gain (Labussière et al., 2016). Interestingly, variations in FHP have been correlated to variations in feeding level, suggesting that maintenance energy requirements are influenced by feeding level (Labussière et al., 2011). This also supports the idea of a combined efficiency of using ME for both maintenance and production. It can be calculated as the complement of the ratio between heat increment and ME and allows for the calculation of NE, which has been proved to better represent the utilization of energy by the animals (Noblet et al., 2024).

Conclusion

To conclude, the improvement in the analysis of gas exchange measurements through mathematical modelling of their high frequency dynamics allows for a better understanding of the energy utilization by producing animals. This has practical consequences for animal feeding, as it updates the knowledge of the energy requirements of animals and the nutritional values of diets and ingredients leading to more sustainable livestock systems.

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4. Models to estimate the energy requirement in broiler chickens

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Abstract

Energy is considered the main factor to meet their requirements through feed intake in broiler chickens. In the factorial approach, energy is designated to maintenance and production (or growth). Determining net energy requirements seems a more direct approach for assessing energy utilization in broiler chickens, since net energy for maintenance (NEm) is determined from direct measurements of fasting heat production (FHP) under standard conditions. The net energy for growth (NEg) is determined as the sum of energy retained as protein (ER_{pt}) and fat (ER_{fat}). The ER, as each protein and fat tissue is obtained from protein and lipid deposition, is multiplied by the energy contribution of each tissue, typically 5.6 kcal/g for protein and 9 kcal/g for fat. In this sense, combining the growth curve model with descriptions of the growth of each component and the experimental determination of the energy requirement, it is possible to develop models to determine NE requirements. Additionally, factors such as the influence of temperature, production density, and energy utilization efficiency can be implemented to adjust requirement models. Based on a mechanistic framework and supported by the growth potential theory, we proposed a factorial model to determine the NE requirement for broiler chickens dynamically.

Keywords: Energy metabolism, energy utilization, modelling, poultry.

Introduction

Energy is considered the main factor influencing feed intake regulation. Birds intake up to meet their energy requirements. However, different energy expressions can be used for poultry, such as metabolizable and net energy, different than swine, where digestible energy is depressed. In this sense, the energy requirement can also be referred to as energy utilization, considering partitioning and fractions, and how each component of the energy is affected by different intrinsic and extrinsic factors for the animal.

Like other nutrients, energy requirement can be partitioned into maintenance and growth, following the factorial approach. This approach helps to identify and quantify the influence of different factors on the proportion of each component of energy utilization. In this sense, factorial models of the energy requirement can represent a useful tool for adapting requirement determination to each specific production condition, making it more flexible and moving toward precise nutrition.

The objective here is to develop models to estimate energy utilization in broiler chickens based on genetic potential, accounting for factors that influence energy demand.

Development of factorial model for energy requirement

The factorial model was constructed based on the growth potential of the whole body and its components, including tissue deposition (e.g., protein, feathers, and fat).

Growth potential

Growth potential descriptions were adapted from data for male Cobb 500 broiler chickens (Goncalves et al., 2018). The growth potential was developed based on the protein deposition (PD) as:

$$PD \left(\frac{g}{d} \right) = BP \times 0.042 \times \ln \left(\frac{1290}{BP} \right)$$

After that, the lipid deposition (LD) is calculated by the relationship between PD, the rate of lipid and protein in maturity (LPm):

$$LD \left(\frac{g}{d} \right) = PD \times 1.43 \times 0.91 \times \left(\frac{BP}{1290} \right)^{1.43-1}$$

The other components of water (WD) and ash (AshD) deposition are calculated by an allometric relationship between PD:

$$WD \left(\frac{g}{d} \right) = EXP(1.98 + 0.89 * \ln(PD))$$

$$AshD \left(\frac{g}{d} \right) = EXP(-1.17 + 0.89 * \ln(PD))$$

Integrating as daily weight gain (BWG) and tissue deposition dynamically, it will be possible to have sufficient information to implement the energy requirement:

$$BWG \left(\frac{g}{d} \right) = PD + LD + WD + AshD$$

A dynamic integration of tissue deposition (e.g., PD) and BWG resulted in the body protein weight (BP), feather weight (FW), and body weight (BW). This variable is used as input in the factorial model for NE and metabolizable energy (ME) requirements.

Energy partitioning

Following the classical approach to energy partitioning, the total energy intake can be lost in different ways (Figure 1), and the remaining fractions are directed to specific destinations (Zwuidoff et al., 2019). This is the foundation for determining the net energy requirement based on maintenance thought FHP and production, which involves the sum of ER_pt and ER_fat.

Gross energy intake (GE_{intake})				Energy loss in excreta
Metabolizable energy (ME)			Heat production (HP)	
Energia retenida (ER)				
ER_{fat}	ER_{pt}	FHP	Heat incremente (HI)	
$NE_{production}$		NE_m		
Net energy (NE)				

Figure 1. Partitioning of energy utilization and description of the different components in poultry.

The NE_m and NE_p were determined, and the ME requirement was subsequently partitioned into maintenance (ME_m), and the ME requirements for protein (ME_{pt}) and fat (ME_{fat}) were determined based on energy utilization efficiency. The effects of stocking density and temperature were adjusted in NE_m , and only temperature affected the efficiency of protein and fat deposition.

Net energy requirement

For energy requirements, the factorial model, where maintenance is represented by FHP, is expressed as an allometric function of $a \times BW^b$, and growth is expressed as energy retention as protein (ER_{pt}) and fat (ER_{fat}).

Net energy for maintenance

The net energy for maintenance can be varied according to the bird category and the determination of the allometric exponent is result of the relationship of BW and FHP (Figure 1).

The determination of the allometric exponent was adopted as 0.75, and the NE_m under normothermia can be $94 (SE \pm 8.2) \text{ kcal/kg}^{0.75}$ (Riveros et al., 2025). However, other factors can influence the maintenance requirement, such as stocking density, which indirectly affects physical activity, and temperature, which influences the energy cost of thermoregulation.

Figure 1. Dispersion plot of all data with connecting line between the same study (A) and dispersion plot considering each study's weight- w based on the n -sample size (B). Box-plot of the allometric exponent distribution reported in the literature for the avian species based on table 5. Allometric exponents are estimated based on the model 1 for each category of growing chickens (\bullet), laying hens (\blacklozenge), roosters (\times) and for all categories (\blacktriangle). Sources: Riveros et al., 2025.

Factors influencing net energy for maintenance

Physical activity and stoking density

A fraction of energy that is not part of the maintenance and also is not destined for growth is expended due to physical activity (PA). However, PA is influenced by available physical space and can vary with age, as reflected in body weight. The available space for chickens, assuming that available feeders and drinkers are not a limiting factor, is strictly related to the stocking density (birds/m² or kg of BW/m²). However, as is known, young birds weighing up to around 0.8 kg BW spent more time in PA and also showed greater displacement (velocity) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Physical activity variation as effect of the BW. Adapted from Tickle et al., 2018.

The model proposed by Tikle et al. (2018), together with the linear relationship between PA and energy expenditure, $HPA \text{ (kcal/min)} = 0.059 + 0.018 \times PA$ (Riveros et al., 2023), enabled the correction of NEm by adding the heat production due to PA (HPA), considering the light program:

$$Activity (\%) = \begin{cases} BW < 0.91; 18.9 - 15.98 \times BW \\ BW \geq 0.91; 4.47 + 0.09 \times BW \end{cases}$$

$$Velocity \text{ (m/min)} = \begin{cases} BW < 0.816; 0.146 - 0.06 \times BW \\ BW \geq 0.816; 0.09 - 0.002 \times BW \end{cases}$$

Considering both functions and photoperiod (e.g., 16L:8D) are calculated as $PA = activity \times velocity \times photoperiod \text{ (min)}$. With a linear relationship, $HPA \text{ (kcal/min)} = 0.059 + 0.018 \times PA$, it is possible to correct NEm by PA.

On the other hand, the social factors influence the energy expended for PA. One of the more prominent is density (D), where a segmented model requires extra energy for each density. For that, a theoretical model fits data from accelerometers and available space per bird and applied to experimental data (Figure 3).

$$HPA(\% \text{ above } NEm) = \begin{cases} D < 27; 12 \\ 27 < D \leq 42; 27.41 + 0.53 \times D \\ D \geq 42; 4.5 \end{cases}$$

With that, NEm is corrected, increasing in percentage the extra energy required depending on the stoking density.

Figure 3. Fit of segmented model of three phases to predict the extra NEm required depending on the stoking density.

Temperature, energy expenditure for thermogenesis and NEm

A mechanistic model was developed that integrates physiological responses and energy expenditure dynamics and accurately predicts TNZ and CT in broiler chickens and laying hens. The primary objective is to develop and validate a model as a function of ambient temperature (T), body weight, and age.

The theoretical model proposed was:

$$NEm = \begin{cases} (Tb - T) * \frac{NEm}{(Tb - CT)}; T < CT \\ NEm + (T - UCT) * \frac{(maxFHP - NEm)}{(Tb - CT)}; T \geq CT \end{cases}$$

The NEm for broiler chickens was estimated at 82.2 kcal/kg^{0.75}, with CT decreasing from 29.4°C at 7 days to 22.7°C at 42 days (Table 1). Additionally, CT and maxFHP were described as a non-linear and linear function of BW:

$$CT = A + (A - B) \times \exp(-k \times BW^{0.75})$$

$$maxFHP = p + q \times BW^{0.75}$$

The parameters of the dynamic model are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1. Parameters to describe the CT in broiler chickens dynamically in function of the BW.

Broiler chickens				
Parameter	Unit	Estimate	Approximate 95% CI	
NEm	kcal/kg ^{0.75}	82.2	79.6	84.7
A	°C	21.5	19.6	23.4
B	°C	11.56	8.71	14.41
k	°C/d	0.918	0.44	1.396
p	kcal/kg ^{0.75}	68.5	54.2	82.7
q	kcal/kg ^{0.75} /d	33	21.7	44.3
Age	CT	Tb	b ₁	b ₂
d	°C	°C	kcal/kg ^{0.75} /°C	kcal/kg ^{0.75} /°C
7	29.4	41.4	6.9	-0.5
14	27.8	41.4	6	0.2
21	26	41.3	5.4	1
28	24.5	41.2	4.9	1.8
35	23.4	41.2	4.6	2.6
42	22.7	41.2	4.5	3.3

These functions can dynamically determine NEm based on heat transfer using temperature differences (T-Tb, T-CT, or CT-T).

Net energy for growth and efficiency of utilization

The NE for growth is determined by multiplying the PD and LD by their respective caloric contributions. As expected, temperature does not just affect NEm but also the efficiency of energy utilization. For that, a series of parameters was adopted to determine the RE_{pt} and RE_{fat}, as well as the ME_{growth}, using their respective efficiencies corrected for temperature (Table 2).

Table 2. Parameters of correction of efficiencies by temperature, considering the thermoneutral zone (TN) for broiler chickens as a reference. Sources Rabello et al., (2006).

Parameters	Abb	Value
Efficiency of maintenance	km_TN	0.80
	km_LCT	0.76
	km_UCT	0.76
Efficiency of fat deposition	kfat_TN	0.60
	kfat_LCT	0.92
	kfat_UCT	0.70
Efficiency of lipid deposition	kpt_TN	0.58
	kpt_LCT	0.36
	kpt_UCT	0.47
Net energy for fat deposition (kcal/g)	REpt	5.67
Net energy for protein deposition (kcal/g)	REfat	9.37

Practical application

The NE requirement model is a useful tool for implementing requirement determination under varying conditions of temperature, stocking density, and genetic strains, based on the theory of genetic potential. In Figure 4, a demonstration shows birds adjusting their requirements for NE and AMEn.

Figure 4. First line of the graph represents the changes in energy requirement for broiler chickens under hot conditions during 21 to 28d. The second line of figures represent the changes of energy requirement for maintenance considering the density effect with 20 birds/m² and 26 birds/m².

Conclusion

The net energy factorial model reflects the "real" energy expended by the birds and can account for factors such as physical activity and temperature. PA is a factor that mainly influences NEm, with a slight impact on the overall requirement. Temperature also varies the requirement demand by influencing NEm and the efficiency of tissue deposition.

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5. Developing models to estimate the energy requirements for laying hens

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Introduction

One of the main challenges in laying hen nutrition lies in how energy is still treated in diet formulation. Despite the genetic advances in modern strains, most diets are still based on empirical systems or fixed recommendations that do not reflect the dynamic nature of energy partitioning within the bird. While hens continuously adjust energy use among maintenance, body deposition, and egg production, traditional models remain static. Furthermore, the use of metabolizable energy (ME) as the primary reference ignores differences in utilization efficiency among physiological functions, limiting the accuracy of nutritional estimates (Barzegar et al., 2019).

Another critical issue is the adoption of fixed requirements by production phase, disregarding key variables such as body weight, body weight change, and egg mass (Silva et al., 2025). As a result, large safety margins are often applied, leading to an oversupply of energy. In practice, this excess energy is not converted into eggs but dissipated as heat, increasing feed costs without productive return. This scenario highlights the need for more precise models that better represent avian metabolism and physiology, enabling more efficient energy utilization.

Methodology

In this context, the Poultry Science Laboratory at UNESP/FCAV developed prediction models for metabolizable energy (AME) and net energy (NE) requirements of laying

hens during the production phase. The study was conducted with Hy-Line W80 hens fed ad libitum, using 30 diets with a wide range of energy levels (2419 to 3096 kcal/kg AME), while maintaining a constant digestible lysine-to-energy ratio. Evaluations were performed using indirect calorimetry, allowing estimation of variables such as heat production, metabolizable energy intake, and energy retention, which was further partitioned into energy retained as protein and fat in both the body and eggs.

Development of models of requirements

Based on these data, nonlinear mixed-effects models were developed, incorporating metabolic body weight ($BW^{0.75}$), body weight change (ΔBW), and egg mass (EM) as parameters. This approach enabled a more comprehensive description of energy utilization dynamics, and the models were defined as presented in table 1.

Model 1 is based on the principle that all energy consumed by the bird is allocated to three main functions: maintenance, body deposition, and egg production. The $BW^{0.75}$ term, grounded in allometric principles, represents metabolic body weight and reflects the non-linear relationship between metabolism and body weight. The component associated with body weight change (ΔBW) introduces the dynamic aspect of the model, allowing consideration of both weight gain and loss throughout the production cycle. Finally, the EM (egg mass) term represents the energy directed toward egg production, which is the most economically relevant component, as it directly reflects the conversion of energy into a marketable product.

Table 1. Parameters of metabolizable and net energy utilization models

Model	Parameters	Estimated	SE	T-value	P-value	RMSE
1	<i>a</i>	81.17	13.12	6.19	<0.001	11.25
	<i>b</i>	0.42	0.21	2.00	0.048	
	<i>c</i>	1.51	0.27	5.59	<0.001	
2	<i>k_m</i>	0.86	0.15	5.71	<0.001	14.00
	<i>k_{body}</i>	0.46	0.14	3.39	0.001	
	<i>k_{egg}</i>	0.64	0.09	6.96	<0.001	

The parameter “a” is estimated per unit for maintenance (kcal/kg^{0.75}), “b” and “c” are the estimated parameters for weight gain (kcal/g*d) and egg production (kcal/g egg mass) respectively, “k_m” is the efficiency of energy utilization for maintenance, “k_{body}” is the efficiency of tissue deposition for body weight gain, “k_{egg}” is the efficiency for egg production.

Model 2 represents an advancement in terms of practical application, as it expresses energy requirements in parameters directly usable in feed formulation. Its main feature is the inclusion of efficiency coefficients (k_m, k_{body}, and k_{egg}), which indicate the proportion of metabolizable energy effectively converted into net energy for each physiological function. These coefficients demonstrate that not all consumed energy is utilized with the same efficiency, as part of it is inevitably lost as metabolic heat, and this loss varies depending on the function performed by the bird.

When validating the models using data from the Lohmann White strain, it was possible to demonstrate their ability to represent the physiological dynamics of birds throughout the production period (Figure 1). Unlike tables and manuals that adopt fixed AME levels based on feed intake, these models clearly identify transitions between production phases. These changes reflect variations in energy demand for maintenance and egg production throughout the cycle. Thus, energy requirements are shown to be dynamic rather than fixed, depending on the physiological state of the bird. In this way, the models provide a more accurate representation of energy utilization and support more efficient nutritional decision-making.

From an economic perspective, energy has a significant impact on diet formulation. Considering that this nutrient represents approximately 60% of total feed cost, even small adjustments in its levels can lead to meaningful cost savings. Based on the ME prediction models, estimated energy levels for peak production, phase 2, and phase 3 were approximately 2766, 2728, and 2666 kcal/kg, respectively, whereas the values commonly used in Brazilian farms average 2823, 2777, and 2722 kcal/kg. This average difference of 55 kcal/kg indicates an important adjustment. Assuming an average feed

cost of R\$ 1,467 per ton, each kcal is estimated to cost around R\$ 0.00032, resulting in savings of approximately R\$ 17.45 per ton when using more precise energy levels. In large-scale systems, such as a farm with 2 million birds and a monthly production of 6,000 tons of feed, this could represent annual savings close to R\$ 1,257,000. Additionally, the use of net energy-based models helps avoid two common formulation errors: energy deficiency, which compromises performance and feed efficiency, and energy oversupply, which increases costs without productive return.

Figure 1. Determination of net energy (NE) and metabolizable energy (ME) requirements for Lohmann White, using models 1 and 2 presented in table 1.

Conclusion

Finally, the robustness of the developed models is directly related to their physiological foundation and the use of measurable field variables such as body weight, body weight change, and egg mass. The adoption of net energy as a nutritional reference, combined with prediction models, allows for more precise adjustment of dietary energy levels, avoiding both deficiencies that impair performance and excesses that unnecessarily increase costs. In this context, this approach represents a

significant advancement in laying hen nutrition, as it more effectively aligns the biological response of birds with the economic viability of production systems.

Acknowledgments

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6. Energy Partitioning and Models to Estimate Metabolizable and Net Energy Requirements for Broiler Breeders

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Abstract

This study evaluated the dynamics of energy partitioning and requirements in broiler breeders from 29 to 65 weeks of age under varying intake levels. Factorial requirement models were developed for both Metabolizable Energy (ME) and Net Energy (NE) systems. Using respirometric chambers, the NE maintenance requirement was found to remain constant at 259 kJ/kg^{0.75}*d. However, body tissue deposition showed a significant effect of energy intake and age, demonstrating that while egg production remains a metabolic priority, the efficiency of nutrient retention and reserve mobilization shifts as birds aged.

The NE system proved superior to the ME system, showing a 40% reduction in predictive error (RMSE of 101 vs. 229) providing a more accurate description of the energy requirements prediction. These results highlight that implementing NE systems, supported by models that capture the longitudinal effects of age, is essential for advancing precision nutrition. In conclusion, considering the dynamic of retained energy partitioning, these models serve as tools for estimating energy demands. However, future models should integrate environmental and behavioral variables to optimize energy requirements under different conditions.

Keywords: Mixed model, energy retention, fasting heat production, energy requirements, energy balance.

Introduction

Genetic selection in broiler breeders has resulted in a voracious appetite and improved energy utilization efficiency, leading to excessive weight gain and fat accumulation, which directly impairs reproductive performance. Therefore, strictly controlling energy intake through feed restriction is the primary strategy to balance maintenance, growth, and egg production (Zuidhof, 2020). Recent evidence suggests that different factors influence energy utilization and the determination of requirements in these birds, including the dynamics of energy allocation to body tissues and egg production, which depend on productive potential and age (Teofilo et al., 2023;). This reinforces the need to better understand this dynamic to improve the determination of energy requirements.

Traditionally, requirements are estimated using the Metabolizable Energy (ME) system through linear models that assume constant efficiencies (Romero et al., 2009). However, this system does not consider the metabolic utilization of energy retained in tissues, which can be elucidated by the Net Energy (NE) system. Studies with swine have already demonstrated that the NE system is more accurate for expressing requirements and the energetic values of feedstuffs (Noblet, 2007). However, for poultry, more research is still needed on requirements and the energetic values of ingredients to consolidate the NE system in commercial nutrition. The first step for this implementation is to understand the dynamics of energy utilization in broiler breeders. Thus, this work examines energy utilization throughout the production period and proposes factorial models to determine ME and NE requirements.

Methodologies

Sixty Cobb 500 broiler breeders were evaluated from 29 to 65 weeks. The feed was provided and controlled in accordance with the management guide. Birds were housed in respirometric chambers to measure gas exchange (VO_2 and VCO_2), establishing three energy intake levels: recommended, 25% above, and 25% below. The protocol consists of one day for bird adaptation to the chambers, two days of

feeding to measure total heat production (THP), and 1.5 days of fasting (FHP). Laboratory analyses included egg, feed, and excreta to determine crude protein and gross energy content. Apparent metabolizable energy intake (AMEi) was determined by the difference between gross energy in feed and excreta, while retained energy (RE) was calculated as AMEi minus THP, and HI was isolated as THP - FHP. The RE was partitioned into body (RE_b) and egg (RE_e) components. These were further divided into protein and fat retention for both the egg (RE_{ep} and RE_{ef}) and the body (RE_{bp} and RE_{bf}), respectively.

Energy balance data were analyzed using linear regression analysis of multiple factors to evaluate the effects of AMEi, age, and their interaction. Factorial models to determine the energy requirement (ME and NE) were performed by mixed models as a function of metabolic body weight (BW^{0.75}), body weight gain (BWG), and egg mass (EM). The ME model included efficiency parameters for maintenance, BWG and egg production (k_m , k_{gain} , k_{egg} respectively). Model accuracy was validated using the root mean square error (RMSE) and regression analysis between observed and predicted values. All statistical processing was performed in SAS, using a 95% confidence interval.

Results and Discussion

Feed intake ranged from 0.103 to 0.196 kg/bird*d, providing an ME gradient (1,126 to 2,311 kJ/bird*d) sufficient to characterize energy partitioning. The maintenance requirement (FHP) remained constant at 259 kJ/kg^{0.75}*d. The RE was highly dependent on the AMEi level and bird age. This dynamic corroborates the findings of Teofilo et al. (2023), where it was observed that the birds transitioned from a high fat deposition phase between weeks 31 and 35 (peak production) to an increase in protein retention during the post-peak period. This metabolic shift in body composition, characterized by fat accumulation followed by changes in protein turnover, aligns with the physiological onset of the decline in egg production (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Overview of metabolizable energy intake partitioning in broiler breeder across weeks (Teofilo et. al., 2023)

This confirms that while egg production is a metabolic priority, the way excess energy is stored in the body changes with age and energy intake. High AME_i is associated with fat deposition, whereas weight loss results from mobilizing reserves to sustain egg production.

A relevant point was the improved energy utilization observed. Similar to Teofilo (2023), who found AME_n values 9% higher than those formulated, this study noted that adult breeders utilized ingredient energy more efficiently. This phenomenon can be attributed to the increased digestive capacity of the birds' gastrointestinal tract with age and longer retention time of digesta in adults due to increased intestinal length. Such evidence highlights the urgency of determining feed energy values by animal category within the ME system or of implementing the NE system to reduce these discrepancies.

Mixed-effects models provided a robust fit for both ME and NE systems, effectively partitioning requirements for maintenance, growth, and egg production through the factorial method. For both systems, requirements were expressed using practical

inputs such as body weight, body weight gain, and egg mass (Table 1). Applying these models to experimental data (Figure 2) demonstrated that the NE system achieved a lower RMSE (101) compared to the ME system (169), suggesting a more precise representation of energy metabolism in broiler breeders during the production phase. Although the ME system exhibited satisfactory predictive capacity, it was outperformed by the accuracy of the NE system.

Table 1. Parameters of metabolizable energy intake utilization models.

Model	Parameters	Estimated	SE	t-value	P-value
1.1	$NE = 318 \times BW^{0.75} + 5.75 \times EO + 11.2 \times BWG$				
	A	318	± 33.63	9.45	***
	P	5.75	± 2.016	2.85	**
	Q	11.2	± 1.019	11	***
1.2	$ME = 357 \times BW^{0.75} + 4.60 \times EO + 14.36 \times BWG$				
	k_m	0.891	± 0.053	16.75	***
	k_{egg}	0.78	± 0.037	5.78	***
	k_{gain}	0.801	± 0.037	21.72	***

a, **p** and **q** are the estimated parameters per unit of maintenance (kJ/kg BW^{0.75}), weight gain (kJ/g BWG) and egg production (kJ/g EO), respectively. **km**: efficiency for maintenance; **kegg**: efficiency for egg production and **kgain**: efficiency of tissue deposition in body weight gain. **SE**: Standard error, **EO**: Egg mass. The probability expressed as * (P<0.05), ** (P<0.01), *** (P<0.001).

Due to the dynamic nature of RE partitioning, mixed models serve as powerful tools for estimating energy demands, as they capture metabolic shifts between egg production and tissue mobilization. For broader practical application, future NE models should integrate environmental and behavioral variables. Within the ME system, as established by Rabello (2004) and Sakomura (2004) factors such as ambient temperature (quadratic effect) and physical activity (a 21% increase in floor-raised birds compared to those in cages) remain critical for maximizing nutritional precision and productive efficiency in broiler breeder hens.

Figure 2. Dispersion plots are used to compare the observed and predicted values of **NE** as described by model 1.1 (**A**), and for **ME** disregarding the age effect as described by model 2.1 (**B**). The observed data take into account the results from the biological trial, while the predicted data were obtained using the models and the variables **BW**, **BWG**, and **EM**. R^2 is the degree of determination, and RMSE is the standard error.

Practical application

Using performance data and recommendations for the Cobb 500 (2026), the model developed in the present study was evaluated against other models from literature and the nutritional goals of the genetic line (Figure 3). It was observed that, when compared to the other curves, the original model tended to underestimate the energy requirements for maintenance. This behavior is attributed to the experimental conditions of indirect calorimetry, in which the birds were individually housed in respirometry chambers at 21°C scenario that minimizes physical activity and reduces FHP.

To adapt the predictions to practical field conditions, two exploratory adjustments to the maintenance requirements were performed: the first integrated the thermoregulatory model developed by the Poultry Science Laboratory at UNESP Jaboticabal, which incorporates the dynamic effects of ambient temperature; the second applied a 21% increase to the baseline maintenance requirement to account for the energy expenditure associated with physical activity in floor-raised birds, as described by Sakomura (2004). The application of these adjustments demonstrated that the estimated values became significantly more coherent and aligned with the recommendations of the Cobb nutritional guidelines (Figure 3). Therefore, as a future

direction, it is suggested that upcoming studies aim to directly and integrally incorporate variables such as ambient temperature, degree of feathering, and physical activity into energy partitioning equations. This integration is essential for maximizing nutritional precision and productive efficiency under commercial conditions.

Figure 3. Predicted AMEI requirement (kcal/d) at 24°C environmental temperature (T_e). Predictions are based on body weight (BW , kg), body weight gain (BWG , g/d), feed intake (FI , g/d), and egg output (EO , g/d) data for Cobb 500 broiler breeder hens (2026) from 25 to 65 weeks of age. The respective equations used for the models evaluated are as follows:

Present study: $AMEI = 85.4 \cdot BW^{0.75} + 3.34 \cdot BWG + 1.76 \cdot EO$

Present study*: Adjusted maintenance coefficient to $ME_m \cdot BW^{0.75}$

Present study:** Adjusted maintenance coefficient to $103.33 \cdot BW^{0.75}$

Pishnamazi et al. (2015): $AMEI = (135.87 - 3.64 \cdot T_e + 0.075 \cdot T_e^2) \cdot BW^{0.84} + (0.1185 \cdot FI) \cdot BW^{0.84} + 2.13 \cdot BWG + 1.79 \cdot EO$

Rabello et al. (2006): $AMEI = BW^{0.75} \cdot 192.76 - 6.32 \cdot T_e + 0.12 \cdot T_e^2 + 7.63 \cdot BWG + 2.4 \cdot EO$

Reyes et al. (2012): $AMEI = BW^{0.75} \cdot 110.3 - 0.47 \cdot T_e + 0.055 \cdot (T_e - 22.5)^2 + 5.8 \cdot BWG + 2.3 \cdot EO$

*The maintenance coefficient (ME_m) was calculated using a piecewise thermoregulation function based on UNESP Jaboticabal parameters: a baseline FHP of $98.7 \text{ kcal/kg}^{0.75}$ within the thermoneutral zone (22 to 23°C), with linear increments for cold stress ($T_e < 22^\circ\text{C}$) and heat stress ($T_e > 23^\circ\text{C}$) up to a maximum FHP of $153 \text{ kcal/kg}^{0.75}$ at body temperature (40.5°C).

** Model adjusted by adding a 21% increase to the baseline maintenance requirement ($76 \text{ kcal/kg}^{0.75}$) to account for the physical activity of floor-raised birds, according to Sakomura (2004).

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7. Quantifying the energetic cost of subclinical disease: effects of health challenges on energy utilization in broiler chickens

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Abstract

This study evaluated the physiological and metabolic adaptations and their effects on energy utilization in broiler chickens subjected to different health challenge models. Two experimental models were used. In the first trial, necrotic enteritis was induced through inoculation with *Eimeria maxima* and *Clostridium perfringens*. In the second trial, birds were challenged with lipopolysaccharide (LPS) to simulate systemic inflammation. Measurements included feed intake, body weight, excreta production, oxygen consumption, carbon dioxide production, and heat production using respirometry techniques. Health challenges reduced feed intake and growth performance, increasing energy expenditure due to immune activation and thermoregulatory responses such as fever. In the LPS model, immune activation contributed an additional 31 kcal/kg^{0.75}/d to total heat production. These findings demonstrate that health challenges impose a significant energetic cost and highlight the importance of nutritional strategies focused on energy supply and targeted amino acid supplementation to mitigate performance losses in broiler production.

Keywords: Energy metabolism, Heat production, Health challenge, Nutritional modeling.

Introduction

Modern broiler chickens are selected for fast growth and high feed efficiency. However, stressors can reduce feed intake and alter nutrient and energy utilization, resulting in poor growth performance. Health challenges are among the most important factors that impede growth by promoting voluntary feed intake depression, a paradoxical increase in energy demand to support the immune response and reduce tissue retention, and, eventually, the mobilization of endogenous sources (Klasing, 2007; Johnson, 1997).

Energy metabolism can reflect the metabolic adjustments of chickens under poor sanitary conditions. Measurements of heat production can reflect the energy cost of thermoregulation and the immune response, elucidating the dynamics of energy utilization in broiler chickens. Between the energy demand and the increase in body temperature (fever), this represents an additional energetic cost for the animal (Ruuskanen et al., 2021). In broiler chickens, these metabolic shifts may alter the partitioning of energy between maintenance, growth, and immune functions.

This study aimed to evaluate the dynamics of energy utilization in broiler chickens under health challenges and determine the energy cost of the immune response.

Experiment 1 – Effects of necrotic enteritis challenge on energy utilization in broiler chickens

To evaluate the impact of enteric disease on energy metabolism, an experiment was conducted using a necrotic enteritis challenge model. A total of 96 male broiler chickens (Cobb 500) were assigned to three treatments: non-challenged birds fed *ad libitum* (AL), challenged birds fed *ad libitum* (C), and non-challenged birds pair-fed to match the feed intake of the challenged group (PF). Necrotic enteritis was induced by oral inoculation with *Eimeria maxima* at 14 days of age, followed by *Clostridium perfringens* from 18 to 20 days of age. Birds were placed in open-circuit respirometry chambers to measure gas exchange. Feed intake, body weight, and excreta

production were recorded to determine energy balance parameters, while oxygen consumption and carbon dioxide production were used to estimate heat production and energy partitioning.

Subclinical enteritis necrotic experimentally induced promotes 22% of feed intake depression during the peak of 4-6DPI, resulting in lower growth. Voluntary feed intake reduction can be influenced by anorexia induced and the specific diseases' effect, which influences energy utilization.

Energy retention drops 4-6 DPI, being the principal source of energy to support immune response, comes from endogenous fat catabolism. The dynamic of residual energy efficiency (Figure 1) evidenced that the anorexic effect is presented before specific pathogen action during the challenge period.

Figure 1. Residual energy efficiency calculated as the relative difference between the observed and predicted energy intake from the *ad libitum* birds to describe the anorexic effect on the energy intake reduction and the effect of the diseases.

Together, these results demonstrate that necrotic enteritis significantly alters energy partitioning in broiler chickens, reducing the efficiency of energy utilization for growth and increasing the energetic cost associated with immune responses.

Experiment 2 – Systemic immune challenge with lipopolysaccharide (LPS)

Systemic inflammation was induced using LPS to evaluate its effects on energy metabolism and physiological responses in broiler chickens. A total of 21 male broilers

(Cobb 500) were assigned at 19 days of age to three treatments: non-challenged control (CON), birds challenged with 10 µg LPS/kg body weight (10LPS), and birds challenged with 100 µg LPS/kg body weight (100LPS). At 21 days, LPS from *Escherichia coli* was administered intramuscularly. Gas exchange variables and core body temperature were continuously recorded for 23 h during fasting. Blood and liver samples were collected for metabolomic analyses.

Heat production increased with body temperature, demonstrating that thermoregulatory responses, such as fever, are associated with higher energy expenditure (Figure 2). Birds challenged with LPS showed a greater increase in heat production with rising Tb, indicating an elevated metabolic cost during immune activation. The partitioning of heat production revealed that immune energy expenditure contributed an additional 31 kcal/kg^{0.75}/d. These results indicate that immune activation diverts a significant proportion of energy toward supporting physiological responses, reducing the energy available for growth.

Figure 2. Relationship between body temperature and heat production, and Partitioning of heat production in broiler chickens. (Tb = body temperature; HP = heat production; FHP = fasting heat production; HI = heat increment; IEE = immune energy expenditure).

Poor sanitary conditions, depending on the degree of animal exposure, reduce energy intake while increasing energy demands to support the immune system. Although nutritional interventions may be limited under these conditions, strategies aimed at

mitigating feed intake reduction can help improve tissue deposition and prevent excessive endogenous catabolism.

Conclusion

Both experimental models demonstrated that health challenges significantly alter energy metabolism and nutrient partitioning in broiler chickens. Intestinal challenge and systemic inflammation reduced performance and increased energy expenditure associated with immune activation. Metabolomic analyses revealed alterations in amino acid, lipid, and energy metabolism, indicating mobilization of endogenous reserves to support the immune response. Notably, changes in amino acids such as arginine and threonine suggest increased demands for immune function, antioxidant defense, and intestinal mucosal integrity, highlighting their indirect role in energy metabolism. These findings emphasize the energetic cost of immune activation and support the development of nutritional strategies aimed at optimizing energy availability and targeted amino acid supply to improve resilience and mitigate performance losses in poultry production.

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8. Impact of the feed form and enzymes on energy utilization and the net energy system

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Abstract

The use of nutritional strategies to reduce the cost of broiler production is well known, such as the use of enzymes and the physical form of the feed, but little is known about energy utilization. The aims of this abstract were to evaluate the effect of phytase supplementation and the physical form of the feed on energy utilization. Trial 1: 160 male broiler chickens (11 – 20-d-old) were randomly allocated to four treatments: positive control (PC), negative control (NC) with reduced nutritional levels and NC with 1000 and 2000 FTU of phytase. Trial 2: 96 (17 – 27-d-old) male broiler chickens were randomly distributed into three treatments: mashed, pelleted and grounded pellet. Total heat production, feed intake and excreta production were measured to calculate apparent metabolizable energy (AME) and corrected by nitrogen balance (AMEn). To calculate the net energy (NE) of the diet, and energy retention in the body. Retained energy (RE) in the body was determined in RE as protein and fat. An effect ($P < 0.05$) was observed on the intake of NE, total RE and RE_p and RE_f, the PC presented values higher than the NC and when the two levels of phytase were added there was a greater content of NE in the diet, and greater retention of energy in the body, equal to PC. An improvement in the availability and use of energy was observed in birds that received pellets, which resulted in a higher RE content, mainly as fat. In conclusion enzyme supplementation improves energy utilization, primarily evidenced in the net

energy system, and the physical form of the feed promotes a greater utilization of metabolizable and net energy.

Keywords: Broiler chickens, energy utilization, exogenous enzyme, phytase, pellets.

Introduction

The energy intake from the oxidation of dietary nutrients is used by poultry for various metabolic functions and tissue deposition. However, variations in the nutritional composition of the diet affect digestibility and energy utilization efficiency; therefore, a fraction of the nutrients is not fully utilized. It is well known that the use of exogenous enzymes improves digestibility and nutrient utilization, especially with phytases, favoring a greater release of calcium, phosphorus, and energy, resulting in improved productive response in poultry (Cowieson et al., 2019). Another factor that can affect the feed intake and performance of these animals is the feed pelleting process, which makes nutrients available through denaturation by partially cooking the diet (Massuquetto et al., 2019). However, there are gaps in our understanding of the effects of enzyme use and the pelleting process on ME partitioning. It is known that heat increment (HI) represents the energy cost of intake, digestion, and physical activity, and reductions in HI can be observed when the strategies are applied. On the other hand, a reduction in net energy for maintenance (NEM) can also be evidenced by the reduction in the energy demand of basal metabolism; in both cases, an increase in tissue deposition is expected, evidenced by the weight gain of the birds.

Methodology

Energy metabolism protocol

At 14-d-old the birds were allocated to six open-circuit respirometric chambers, and after five days for adaptation to diets and chambers, CO₂ production and O₂ consumption were measured, and heat production (HP) was calculated. Total excreta collection was performed to nitrogen balance and metabolizable energy determination.

The birds were fed ad libitum. The AME of diets was determined, and the heat increment (HI) was calculated by the difference between HP and a fasting heat production ($107 \text{ kcal/kgBW}^{0.75}$). The respiratory quotient (RQ) was calculated as a rate of CO₂ production and O₂ consumption. The net energy (NE) was calculated by the difference between AME and HI. The efficiency of AME utilization was determined by relation of NE:AME, and energy retention in the body was determined by difference between AME intake and HP.

Trail 1. Phytase supplementation and energy metabolism trail

A total of 160 one-d-old male Ross 308 broiler chickens were randomly distributed into four treatments with five replications of eight birds per experimental unit. The treatments consisted of a nutrient adequate positive control (PC); a negative control (NC) with nutritional reduction of calcium (0.21 %), available phosphorus (0.21 %), SID Lys (0.03% p) and metabolizable energy (55 kcal/kg) vs. the PC; and two levels of the phytase supplementation at 1,000 and 2,000 FTU/kg in the NC.

Trail 2. Feed form and energy metabolism trail

A total 96 one-day-old male Cobb 500 broiler chickens were randomly distributed into three treatments with four replications of eight birds per experimental unit. The treatments consisted of a diet that met the requirements by Rostagno et al. (2017) in mashed, pelleted and grounded pellet. At 21-d-old the birds were allocated to six open-circuit respirometric chambers, after five days for adaptation to diets and chambers, CO₂ production and O₂ consumption were measured, and heat production was calculated.

Data were subjected to ANOVA one way, and Tukey HSD's test was applied to compare the treatments, using Minitab v.19.

Results

In the phytase supplementation trial, no significant effect ($P>0.05$) was shown between treatments for AME, however, the NE of PC (2,434 kcal/kg) was greater than NC (2,245

kcal/kg), and the phytase supplementations (1,000 and 2,000 FTU/kg) showed similar (2,306 and 2,370 kcal/kg, respectively) to PC, and not differing from NC ($p < 0.05$). The efficiencies of energy utilization were 0.74, 0.71, 0.72, and 0.73, for PC, NC, supplementation of 1,000 and 2,000 FTU/kg, respectively. Treatments had no effect on HP and HI ($p > 0.05$). Lower RQ (0.91) was observed for NC ($p < 0.05$) than the other treatments (0.95, 0.95, and 0.96, for PC, NC supplementation of 1,000 and 2,000 FTU/kg, respectively). Energy retention in the body was higher ($p < 0.05$) for PC and 2000 FTU/kg supplementation.

In the feed form trial, no significant effect ($p > 0.05$) was observed for AME and AMEn. However, there was significance of 0.064 and 0.059, respectively. Comparing the mash, pellet and grounded pellet treatments, there was an effect ($p < 0.05$) differing in the values between pellets and grounded pellet, with a higher ME and AMEn content for the pelleted feed. For the NE values of the feed, there was only a significance $p = 0.092$ with the NE value of the pelleted feed higher than that the grounded pellet treatment. The efficiencies of utilization AME to NE were not significantly different ($p > 0.05$), but the pelleted diets presented an efficiency 5% higher than the mashed diet. The mashed feed presented, numerically, higher HP (170 vs 161 kcal/kg^{0.75}) and HI (85.5 vs 76.4 kcal/kg^{0.75}), than the pelleted feeds, and the RQ did not differ between treatments. Birds that received mashed and grounded pellet diets had lower energy retention in the body ($p < 0.05$) and fat retention ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the NE system most efficiently established efficacy of the novel consensus bacterial 6-phytase variant supplementation on energy utilization and metabolism. This is demonstrated by higher energy retention and nutrient oxidation rates, as expressed by the RQ in birds fed with the phytase supplemented diets. For the feed form, a gain in NE was evidenced when pelleted feed was provided, as was higher energy utilization and consequently greater energy retention in the body,

preferably as fat, evidencing that the NE system represents better the energy utilization being favorable to express the energy value depending on the feed form.

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9. Comparison between the traditional metabolizable energy system versus the net energy system on performance and predictability of power

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Abstract

Energy is the first component in feed cost and is considered as primary limiting factor on feed intake regulation. The metabolizable energy (ME) system is currently the main system to feed formulation, but it disregards the heat increment. Net energy (NE) is presented as innovative system due to considering all energy loss fractions. However, require students to demonstrate their accuracy to predict performance response. This study compared the accuracy of the ME and NE systems in predicting broiler chicken and laying hens performance. Trail 1: 2,520 Cobb 500 chickens were used, distributed in a completely randomized design with 12 treatments and seven replicates, subjected to different energy levels (2,900, 3,050, and 3,200 kcal/kg for ME and 2,250, 2,350, and 2,450 kcal/kg for NE), maintaining a standardized ratio of 3.95 g of digestible ileal lysine per Mcal of ME. Weight gain (BWG), feed conversion ratio (FCR), and carcass (CR) and breast (BR) yields were evaluated. Trail 2: 672 laying hens Bovans white randomly distributed in 12 treatments with seven repetition and six birds per treatment. Quadratic regression models were fitted and evaluated using the F-test ($P < 0.05$). Both systems showed quadratic behavior, with increasing responses up to optimal energy

levels. However, the ME system showed a better statistical fit, with higher coefficients of determination (R^2) and lower errors at 28 and 42 days, as well as superiority for carcass characteristics. It is concluded that, although EL is conceptually more robust, the ME system is more reliable under current practical conditions, while EL still requires methodological refinement, especially in the prediction equations and the amino acid:energy ratio, for efficient application in poultry nutrition.

Keywords: Prediction; precision nutrition; energy metabolism; efficiency.

Introduction

As broiler genetic selection advances, their nutritional requirements must be continually adjusted, especially with regard to energy intake, which plays a central role in feed efficiency, productive performance, and production costs (Zuidhof et al., 2015; Wu et al., 2020).

Energy requirements in poultry are expressed based on the metabolizable energy (ME) system, due to its methodological simplicity and wide practical applicability (Pesti & Edwards, 1983; Wu et al., 2020). However, this system assumes constant energy utilization efficiencies and disregards the heat increment (HI) associated with the processes of digestion, absorption, and metabolism of nutrients. In this context, diet composition has a direct influence on energy partitioning, since conventional and alternative ingredients have different energy utilization efficiencies (Rivera-Torres et al., 2010; Musigwa et al., 2021).

A more physiologically accurate approach to describing energy utilization is the net energy (NE) system. Unlike the metabolizable energy (ME) system, which only considers energy losses in excreta, the NE system incorporates the quantification of heat increment (HI), estimated by methodologies such as comparative slaughter and indirect calorimetry. This approach allows for a more accurate determination of the fraction of energy available for tissue maintenance and deposition processes (De Groote, 1974; Swick et al., 2013; Noblet et al., 2024).

Although more biologically accurate, the use of NE in poultry nutrition is still limited by methodological challenges and the scarcity of validated equations for broilers. It is hypothesized that the accuracy in predicting productive performance differs between the net energy (NE) and metabolizable energy (ME) systems. Thus, the objective of this study is to evaluate the formulation of broiler diets based on the EL system, comparing its accuracy in predicting productive performance in relation to the traditional EM system.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted at the Poultry Science Laboratory of the São Paulo State University "Júlio de Mesquita Filho" (Jaboticabal Campus, SP, Brazil).

A total of 2,520 male Cobb 500 broiler chickens, 14 days old, were distributed in a completely randomized design, with 12 treatments, 7 replicates and 30 birds per experimental unit (84 units), housed in a negative pressure shed, with temperature control, wood shavings bedding, tubular feeders and nipple drinkers. The lighting program followed the recommendations for the strain.

The diets were formulated based on the metabolizable energy (ME) and net energy (NE) systems, with levels of 2,900, 3,050 and 3,200 kcal/kg (EM) and 2,250, 2,350 and 2,450 kcal/kg (EL), considering utilization efficiencies of 70% and 80%. The ratio of 3.95 g of ileal digestible lysine standardized by Mcal of EMAN was maintained, according to Rostagno et al. (2024).

Performance was evaluated at 28 and 42 days by means of body weight, feed intake (FI), weight gain (WG) and feed conversion ratio (FCR), corrected for mortality according to the methodology of Sakomura and Rostagno (2016). At 42 days, two birds per experimental unit were slaughtered for evaluation of carcass yield (CR) and breast yield (CR).

Performance and yield data were analyzed using the PROC GLM procedure of the SAS software (SAS On Demand for Academics, Version 9.4, SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC).

USA). Quadratic regression models were fitted to evaluate the effects of energy systems on the GP and CA response variables, RC. The significance of the regression models was assessed using the F-test, considering $P < 0.05$. The fit of the models was evaluated based on the coefficient of determination (R^2), coefficient of variation (CV), mean squared error (MSE), root mean squared error (RMSE), Akaike information criterion (AIC), corrected Akaike criterion (AICC), Bayesian information criterion (BIC), and Mallows' $C(p)$.

Results

At 28 days, the quadratic models for BWG and FCR were significant ($p < 0.0001$), indicating that the effect of energy levels increases to an optimum point, followed by stabilization or reduction of the response. The models for ME showed low AIC and BIC values, as well as reduced CV and errors, demonstrating good fit and high precision (Table 1). Furthermore, the fits were superior for ME ($R^2 = 0.9752$ and 0.9603 ; figures 1 and 2) compared to NE ($R^2 = 0.8734$ and 0.9063). Next, the regression adjustments for the net energy system are presented (Figure 1).

Table 1. Body weight gain (BWG) and feed conversion ratio (FCR) at 28 days, as a function of ME and NE levels.

Variable	ME		NE	
	BWG (kg/ave)	FCR	BWG (kg/ave)	FCR
Intercept(β_0)	-7.4291	13.916	-3.039	7.7034
Energy (β_1)	0.0048	-0.0072	0.0027	-0.0042
Energy ² (β_2)	6.90E-07	1.00E-06	-4.50E-07	7.20E-07
Model (p-value)	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
R^2	0.98	0.96	0.87	0.91
CV (%)	3.3	3.56	7.46	5.46
Root MSE	0.03	0.06	0.07	0.09
MSE	0	0	0.01	0.01
AIC	-65.98	-52.52	-46.41	-42.22
AICC	-60.27	-46.8	-40.69	-36.5
BIC	-76.2	-62.7	-56.6	-52.4
C(p)	3	3	3	3

β_0 = intercept; β_1 = linear effect of energy level; β_2 = quadratic effect of energy level; ME= metabolizable energy; NE = net energy; BWG = body weight gain; FCR = feed conversion ratio; AIC = Akaike information criterion; BIC = Bayesian information criterion.

In the 42-day period, the quadratic models for BODY weight gain (BWG) and feed conversion ratio (FCR) were significant ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the effect of energy levels promotes a response in the variables evaluated.

Figure 1. Quadratic regression fits between metabolizable energy levels and body weight gain (BWG) and feed conversion rate (FCR) of broiler chickens at 28 days

The models for ME showed lower AIC and BIC values, as well as lower CV and errors, showing a better fit (Table 2). The adjustments were superior for ME ($R^2 = 0.9155$ and 0.8461 ; Figure 2) compared to NE ($R^2 = 0.7691$ and 0.6758 ; Figure 2).

Table 2. Body weight gain (BWG) and feed conversion ratio (FCR) at 42 days as a function of ME and NE levels.

Variable	ME		NE	
	BWG (kg/ave)	FCR	BWG (kg/ave)	FCR
Intercept(β_0)	-15.71	38.7581	-6.5189	17.8056
Energy (β_1)	0.0099	-0.0217	0.0054	-0.011
Energy ² (β_2)	1.43E-07	3.19E-07	9.12E-07	1.90E-07
Model (p-value)	<0.0001	0.0002	0.0014	0.0063
R ²	0.9155	0.8461	0.7691	0.6758
CV (%)	9.2751	13.179	15.337	19.1271
Root MSE	0.112	0.3024	0.1853	0.439
MSE	0.0125	0.0914	0.0343	0.1927
AIC	-35.9732	-12.1498	-23.9029	-3.2103
AICC	-30.259	-6.4355	-18.1886	2.5039
BIC	-46.1955	-22.372	-34.1251	-13.4325
C(p)	3	3	3	3

¹ β_0 = intercept; ² β_1 = linear effect of energy level; ³ β_2 = quadratic effect of energy level; ⁴ME= metabolizable energy; ⁵NE = net energy; ⁶BWG = body weight gain; ⁷FCR = feed conversion ratio; ⁸AIC = Akaike information criterion; ⁹BIC = Bayesian information criterion.

After that, the regression adjustments for the net energy system at 42 days of age of the birds are presented (Figures 2).

Figure 2. Quadratic regression fits between metabolizable energy levels and body weight gain (BWG) and feed conversion rate (FCR) of broiler chickens at 42 days.

In the performance analysis (Table 3), the quadratic models were significant ($p < 0.01$) for all variables. Overall, the ME system showed a better fit, with higher R² values (0.9266 and 0.8604) and lower errors (CV and MSE), while NE showed lower predictive

capacity (R^2 between 0.7255 and 0.7603). Furthermore, the lower AIC, AICC, and BIC values observed for ME reinforce the superiority of the fit compared to the NE system. Thus, ME demonstrated greater accuracy in estimating the CY and BY variables.

Table 3. Carcass yield (CY) and breast yield (BY) as a function of metabolizable energy (ME) and net energy (NE) levels.

Variable	⁴ ME		⁵ NE	
	CY (%)	BY (%)	CY (%)	BY (%)
Intercept (β_0)	-79.9678	-44.6575	8.0265	-1.3461
Energy (β_1)	0.0903	0.0482	0.0455	0.0266
Energy ² (β_2)	-0.00001309	-0.00000721	-0.000000771	-0.00000479
Model (p-value)	<0.0001	0.0001	0.0016	0.0030
R²	0.9266	0.8604	0.7603	0.7255
CV (%)	1.2358	1.5694	2.2332	2.201
Root MSE	0.9046	0.546	1.6348	0.7657
MSE	0.8184	0.2981	2.6727	0.5863
AIC	14.1439	2.026	28.345	10.1423
AICC	19.8582	7.7503	34.0593	15.8566
BIC	3.9217	-8.1961	18.1228	-0.0798
C(p)	3.0000	3.0000	3.0000	3.0000

¹ β_0 = intercept; ² β_1 = linear effect of energy level; ³ β_2 = quadratic effect of energy level; ⁴ME = metabolizable energy; ⁵NE = net energy; ⁶CY = carcass yield; ⁷BY = breast yield; ⁸AIC = Akaike information criterion; ⁹BIC = Bayesian information criterion.

Following, the regression adjustments for the net energy system at 42 days of age of the birds are presented (Figures 3).

Figure 3. Quadratic regression fits between metabolizable energy levels and carcass yield (CY) and breast yield (BY).

Performance of the models and prediction accuracy

The quadratic models indicated that both energy systems described the biological responses; however, the metabolizable energy (ME) system presented a higher coefficient of determination and a lower prediction error, demonstrating greater accuracy for both performance variables (GP and CA) and yield characteristics (RC and RP). This superiority is associated with its widespread consolidation in poultry nutrition due to its simpler and more direct determination, which leads to the robust database available, improving the calibration of the equations and the prediction of performance, highlighting this system as a reliable estimate of the energy available for production (NRC, 1994; Zuidhof, 2019; Rostagno et al., 2024).

The lower predictive capacity observed for the net energy (NE) system may be more associated with methodological than conceptual limitations. Net energy estimation considers that nutrients are used with different efficiencies, penalizing the protein fraction due to the greater caloric increment and favoring lipids due to their greater energy efficiency (Van Milgen & Noblet, 2003; Wu et al., 2019; Noblet et al., 2024). In

this context, the accuracy of the predictions depends directly on the proper adjustment of the equations that describe these relationships. When these models still require refinement, their sensitivity to variations in the composition of ingredients, especially in protein and fat content, can result in greater uncertainty in the estimates.

An important factor that may have influenced the results is related to the formulation criteria of experimental diets. Although a constant ratio of 3.95 g of standardized ileal digestible lysine per Mcal of MEAn was maintained, ensuring the balance between amino acids and energy, the diets were formulated based on two distinct energy systems (metabolizable energy and net energy). Evidence indicates that the ideal amino acid-to-energy ratio is not fixed across systems, differing when expressed in terms of ME or NE, with distinct values for Lys:AME and Lys:NE (Yu et al., 2026).

By adopting the amino acid:energy ratio based exclusively on MEn, there may have been a mismatch in diets formulated under the net energy system, resulting in variations in the relative supply of amino acids compared to the energy available for maintenance and protein deposition. This inconsistency may partly explain the lower accuracy of NE-based models and highlights the importance of adjusting this ratio directly based on net energy in order to improve comparability between systems and the interpretation of results.

Conclusion

The metabolizable energy (ME) and net energy (NE) systems represent distinct approaches to energy assessment in broiler chickens. While net energy (NE) incorporates caloric increment and has a stronger physiological basis, the metabolizable energy (ME) system showed greater accuracy in predicting productive performance and carcass characteristics, with better fit and lower errors compared to NE, reflecting its greater robustness and applicability in current diet formulation conditions.

Despite this, net energy has the potential to improve the estimation of the energy value of ingredients, especially in scenarios with greater nutritional variability. However, its practical application still depends on methodological adjustments, such as the refinement of prediction equations and the adequacy of the amino acid-energy ratio. Thus, although NE represents a promising approach in the context of precision nutrition, the ME system remains, at the moment, the main reference for use in commercial poultry production.

Implications of using net energy in poultry nutrition

The metabolizable energy (ME) system remains the most reliable approach for formulating broiler diets, due to its greater accuracy under commercial conditions. The use of net energy (NE) requires caution, especially regarding the adjustment of equations and the composition of ingredients.

When adopting EL, it is essential to define the ideal relationship between amino acids and energy. EL can be advantageous in diets with greater variability of ingredients, such as co-products and by-products. Thus, EL should be used as a complementary tool, while ME remains as a practical reference.

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10. Practical application of net energy system in commercial feed formulation for poultry

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Abstract

The metabolizable energy (ME) system values feed but ignores the differential efficiency with which nutrients are used, charging no energetic penalty for the heat increment generated during nutrient metabolism. The net energy (NE) system corrects this by integrating the feed energy value (the “fuel”) with the animal’s (the “machine”) biological utilization. This contribution summarizes a coherent body of work, from the nutritional origin of NE, through prediction equations and ingredient re-ranking, to validated diet formulation, and shows that NE-based formulation re-orders ingredient value, exposes the energetic cost of dietary protein that ME conceals, and translates into lower feed cost (R\$1.68 → R\$1.39/kg, -17%) and higher energetic efficiency (0.76 → 0.79) at equal ME and digestible lysine. A set of hands-on exercises is proposed to make the system operational for nutritionists.

Keywords: Broiler chickens, feeds, nutrients, least-cost.

“Why net energy” can be implemented in practical feed formulations

As is well known, around 70% of production corresponds to over-feed cost, and energy is the major component responsible for the variation in feed cost (around 60%). However, this refers to the apparent metabolizable energy (AME) system, and its optimization can reduce this fraction of feeding costs. Meanwhile, with the

implementation of net energy (NE) that accounts for all the energy loss fractions, this optimization procedure can be optimized more accurately. Principal macronutrients such as protein, fat, and starch can contribute to energy value, but they are used by birds with varying efficiencies of utilization. The NE accounts for the heat increment (HI), reflecting the energy available for maintenance and tissue deposition.

Conceptually, NE integrates two components, different than AME, which keeps them separated; the requirement (machine) and the feed (fuel) are considered together. These abstracts address the biological implications of NE as a tool for the decision-making process that a nutritionist uses.

Nutritional implications of HI and NE

The HI varied by nutrients. Marginal HI per percentage of dietary nutrients estimated 18.4 Δ kcal/% for crude protein, 10.02 Δ kcal/% for ether extract, and only 1.56 Δ kcal/% for carbohydrates (Figure 1). Protein is a more expensive source of nutrients to metabolize and contributes to HI (76 kcal/g for CP, 48 kcal/kg for fat, and 17 kcal/kg for CHOs). This single result is the key evidence of the combination of nutrients that can optimize energy utilization by the NE system.

Figure 1. Contribution of the heat increment of the principal macronutrients in diets for broiler chickens.

Predicting NE equations and robustness

The methodological approach to obtaining NE values for ingredients involves indirect calorimetry and/or energy balance trials, which constitute a difficult and complex procedure. Prediction equations based on the feed chemical composition can improve their practical application (Table 1).

Table 1. Net energy equations to predict the energy value of feeds on broiler chickens.

Source	Net energy prediction equation (kcal/kg DM)
Riveros et al. (under review)	$NE = 0.815 \times AME - 12.80 \times CP + 14.76 \times EE$
Tay-Zar et al. (2024)	$NE = 0.811 \times AME - 6.22 \times CP + 4.78 \times EE - 11.7 \times CF$
Wu et al. (2018)	$NE = 0.781 \times AME - 6.70 \times CP + 6.94 \times EE$

Some points need to be considered for practical implications. First, the AME coefficients are stable across equations (0.808 ± 0.013), indicating that NE is robustly predicted by AME across datasets. Second, CP varied 40% (coefficient of variation) among equations. In other words, equations disagree mainly about how heavily penalize protein, which is exactly where AMEn is blind. A practical corollary is that when ingredient or diet composition varies by less than ~10%, the equations converge and any of them is adequate; divergence appears precisely in low- or high-protein diets, where the choice of equation matters most.

Net energy re-organized ingredient value

Applying the equations to a common ingredient matrix shows that NE does not simply rescale AME; it changes the ranking. Corn gluten meal, the highest-AME ingredient in the set (3705 kcal/kg), falls to mid-pack on a NE basis (2200 kcal/kg), overtaken by maize (3364 AME but 2666 NE), sorghum (2527 NE), and millet (2460 NE). Across the matrix, energy-dense, starch- and oil-rich ingredients gain rank under NE, while protein-rich meals (corn gluten meal, poultry meal, fish meal, soybean meal) lose rank, consistent with the high HI of protein established in Section 2. For purchasing and least-cost decisions, this means an ingredient's value is system-dependent: an

ingredient that looks expensive per AME kcal may be competitive per NE kcal, and vice versa.

Evaluation of reduced CP diets

Because the equations differ chiefly in the protein term, low-CP diets are the critical test. Predictions were compared against NE measured by indirect calorimetry in broiler diets formulated at 17.5, 19.5, and 21.5% CP (Table 2).

Table 2. Measured vs. predicted NE (kcal/kg DM feed) in reduced-CP broiler diets. NE measured by indirect calorimetry.

Diet CP (%)	Measured NE	Eq. 1	Eq. 2	Eq. 3
17.5	2570	2497	2385	2415
19.5	2573	2542	2496	2493
21.5	2632	2605	2644	2597
RMSE (kcal/kg)	—	27	89.8	78.6
Total error (kcal/kg)	—	80	125	119

Equation 1 reproduced the calorimetric values most accurately, with the lowest RMSE (27.0 vs. 89.8 and 78.6 kcal/kg) and total error (80 vs. 125 and 119 kcal/kg), and it tracked the diets best at the lowest CP—the region of greatest commercial interest given the move toward amino-acid-supplemented, low-protein diets. Reassuringly, all three equations were close at 21.5% CP, confirming that equation choice is second order in conventional diets but first-order in reduced-protein programs.

From prediction to practical formulation

The decisive test of any energy system is whether it produces better diets. Two broiler diets were formulated to the same metabolizable energy (3100 kcal/kg) and the same digestible lysine (1.02%): a conventional maize–soybean meal diet, and a NE-aware diet that opened the ingredient matrix to alternatives (millet, sorghum, cottonseed meal) whose NE value is favorable relative to their price. The NE-aware diet reduced feed cost from R\$1.678 to R\$1.386/kg (–R\$0.29/kg, –17%), lowered crude protein from 18.1% to 16.9%, and raised both net energy (2333 → 2462 kcal/kg) and energetic efficiency, expressed as NE/MEn (0.76 → 0.79). Extending this to a series of diets at

near-constant AMEn (~3055–3100 kcal/kg) revealed a central practical lesson: AMEn was essentially independent of dietary CP, whereas NE declined as CP increased. AMEn hides the energetic penalty of surplus protein; NE prices it. Formulating on NE therefore rewards exactly the levers, moderate protein reduction, judicious use of fat, and alternative energy sources, that lower cost without sacrificing available energy.

Conclusion

Net energy is not just a sophisticated expression of energy value, but also an alternative to optimize energy utilization by reducing HI, promoting CP reduction, and encouraging the inclusion of digestible amino acids. By implementing the NE system, it can reorganize the energy value and prioritize different energy inclusion in the least-cost feed formulation.

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11. Fundamental principles of modeling in poultry nutrition (experience from other species)

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Background

Systems to express the nutritional value of feed ingredients and the requirements of the animal are essential in feed formulation. Over the course of time, different systems have been developed to express the values of energy (e.g., DE, ME, and NE) and amino acids (e.g., AID and SID). Two key aspects are crucial to any of these systems:

- Values and requirements are expressed on the same scale
- Values are assumed to be additive so that the value of the diet equals the sum of the values of the ingredients

Although these aspects may seem obvious, it is not uncommon to see (experienced) nutritionists making errors with this and a simple example can be used to illustrate this. The difference between the standardized ileal digestibility and the apparent ileal digestibility of an amino acid is that the former accounts for the basal endogenous losses due to dry matter intake. The SID values of amino acids are therefore lower than the AID values. But what happened to these basal endogenous losses? By using a SID system, the basal endogenous losses have become part of the "value" side of the system and are no longer part of the "requirement" side. Therefore, both the value of the diets and ingredients and the requirement are lower in a SID system compared to an AID system.

The basis of NE was established more than a century ago (Armsby and Fries, 1915), and different research groups have carried extensive experimental research programs to determine the NE values of feed ingredients and the NE requirements of the animal, and UNESP's activities in poultry (and thus this conference) is a good example of this. Key to these research programs is that they intend to cover a very wide range of ingredients by developing equations that allow to calculate the NE value from the chemical composition of the ingredient or by adjusting measured DE or ME (or AMEn) values via the chemical composition. In the adjusted equations, a higher fat content results in a higher NE value, and higher protein or fiber contents lower the NE value. The NE system is thus based on chemical adjustment factors. There is currently a discussion on-going (mainly in the USA) about the net energy value of soybean meal (SBM) relative to that of corn. In most energy systems, the DE value of SBM is similar to that of corn, but its value is lower in an ME system, and even around 70% of that of corn in a NE system. The lower ME and NE values are due to the protein content in SBM, because not all dietary protein will be retained by the animal and part of it will be excreted as urea or uric acid in the urine, contributing to the energy loss in a ME system). Moreover, there is not only an energy cost associated with protein deposition, but also with the synthesis of urea and uric acid. Dietary protein is thus associated with an energy cost (i.e., either for protein deposition or for nitrogen excretion in the urine) and this has been quantified by research groups working on NE using a wide range of protein sources. The claim that the NE value of SBM is similar or even higher than that of corn raises different questions. As indicated earlier, NE is based on chemical adjustment factors and if the value of SBM is similar to that of corn, the higher value should hold for all protein-containing ingredients. An alternative explanation may be that there are bioactive compounds (e.g., isoflavones, saponins, fiber) in SMB that have a positive effect on the animal. Such a positive effect may occur through an improved gut health (i.e., lower energy expenditure). One can therefore argue that the beneficial effects of SMB (if confirmed) do not affect the "value" side of the equation, but rather the "requirement" side.

This rather long introduction is to illustrate the limitations of nutritional systems based on “values” and “requirements”. These systems definitely have their beauty because of the simplicity and additivity, but we have to be aware (more) that some properties apply only to the diet (e.g., GE and the amino acid content) and other properties apply only to the animal (e.g., retained protein and lipid, ATP), and that anything in-between results from the interaction of the animal with its diet, and this is where modeling comes into the picture. In modeling, the notion of “values” and “requirements” are replaced by the “response” of the animal to its diet. The word response already indicates that it is not fixed and both the diet and the animal change during the production period. A protein ingredient in a well-balanced diet may be used efficiently for protein deposition in a young animal, but the same ingredient in the same diet will be used less efficiently in an older animal. It is the same ingredient, but the animal has changed and so has the “value” of that ingredient for the animal.

Many biologists associate modeling with mathematics and, apart from quantitative geneticists, consider it not “their cup of tea”. It is my believe that the modeling community has done too little to demystify modeling (e.g., by talking about “mathematical modeling” rather than “biological modeling”). Also, models have been made available as user-friendly tools. Whittemore and Whittemore published one of the first nutritional models for monogastric animals, and this model was published more than 50 years ago. It is based on some very simple and accessible concepts that the animal is composed of protein, lipid, water, and ash, and that body weight gain mainly occurs because of the associate of protein and water. Simple (empirical) relationships were proposed between protein, water, and ash, and the sum of the four components makes up the body of the animal. Body weight gain was thus driven by changes in protein and lipid deposition. Protein deposition itself was determined by the protein and amino acid content in the diet. However, an ever-increasing protein supply will not result in a greater protein deposition, and the latter was thus limited by the genetic and phenotypic potential to deposit protein. Some additional relationships were included to account for the fact that animals become fatter with increasing body

weight. This description of Whittemore's model is based on concepts, that we can agree or disagree on, as biologists.

Almost all models that have been developed since then are based on the same concepts. For chickens, we may have differential proteins for feathers and for other body proteins, but this has not fundamentally changed the concepts proposed by Whittemore and Fawcett. The approach if animals grow because they eat (push) or they eat because they want to become mature (pull) reflects different views on the driving forces for growth.

When I was a student in Wageningen in the mid-1980s, I remember discussions that models will replace tables of "values" and "requirements". It is now 40 years later, and this has not been the case and raises the question of the cause of this? First of all, it is the simplicity, robustness, and transparency of the "table system" and these are arguments that will remain. Second, it is my feeling that the modeling community focused too much on the model (with its perceived mathematical complexity) without addressing how people should use it. We developed wonderful engines, but forgot that one needs a car, steering wheel, and airbags to drive a car. It has been my experience that it takes more time to develop the car than to develop the engine (even Whittemore's model can be put in a Ferrari). Also, you don't need to be a car mechanic to drive a car; some nutritionists just want a requirement value and looking it up in a table is much easier than trying to find it through a model (or tool, if available).

So, what should we do, as a modeling community, to make modelling and models more accessible for biologists? Most of the answers can be found in what I already wrote, and this starts with discussing the concepts with nutritionists, without any mathematics. It is my belief that all nutritionists can and should be able to draw a diagram of their research area, in terms of "what drives what?". Once this is agreed upon, modelers can translate this into a model. Secondly, we should put more focus on the development of model-based tools. Some nutritionists may be interested in how it works, others are not, but having the nutritional community work with model-

based tools will definitely help us to make the models and tools better and develop new research questions. Also, training is crucial; and this is an essential element in the training of future nutritionists. The last point relates to data: some 10 to 15 years ago, I thought modeling had come close to an end. The changes relative to Whitemore's model were modest and there were little new things to add. This has completely changed with the availability of data. In the past, we had to imagine a feed intake curve whereas nowadays it can be measured daily (at least in pigs). The availability of data has renewed the interest in modeling, for example for precision livestock nutrition. The downside with data (and artificial intelligence) may be that we think it can be done without the concepts. The key question is then "who needs an animal nutritionist if we have big data and AI"?

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12. Perspectives for implementing modeling in the poultry industry

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Introduction

Poultry production systems require repeated decisions on nutrient density, feed phase changes, ingredient substitution, stocking density, seasonal adaptation, target market weight, and environmental sustainability objectives. In many situations, new experimental evidence cannot arrive in time to guide the decision. Even a single controlled trial requires time, and robust conclusions often depend on multiple flock cycles, which makes the process slow and resource-intensive. Nevertheless, Fisher (2015) emphasized that the most widely used model in applied poultry science is still the pen trial, in which the commercial system is represented by replicated small groups of birds under controlled conditions. This approach has been highly successful and has provided much of the technical foundation for poultry production. However, it remains empirical, applies directly only to the conditions under which the trial was conducted, and is often repeated when genotypes, environments, ingredients, or local production systems change.

Mathematical and biological models should therefore be viewed as complements to experimentation rather than replacements for it. They can extend the value of existing data, organize biological knowledge, and allow scenarios to be evaluated before changes are implemented in the field. Classical model classification remains useful in this discussion. France and Thornley (1984) described models according to three important dimensions, namely empirical or mechanistic, deterministic or stochastic,

and static or dynamic. Fisher (2015) proposed a broader practical framework for poultry modeling, including models of scientific theories, extensions of pen-trial data, growth curves, empirical and mechanistic production models, and real-time control models. That broader view is especially relevant for industry, where scientific classification remains important but does not fully explain how models are used in practice.

For industrial use, the central question becomes practical. What decision does the model support, how quickly can it provide useful guidance, and how much confidence can users place in its outputs? A model may be scientifically sound and still have limited value if it is disconnected from commercial decisions, local calibration, economic interpretation, or practical adoption by technical teams and customers. This text argues that implementation in the poultry industry is best understood as a progression of decision-support capability, moving from tables toward optimization, while AI, hybrid, and integrated systems remain future directions. The discussion first revisits scientific classifications from an industrial point of view, then explains why industry uses models, presents the staircase of modeling progression, examines the current AI wave, and closes by emphasizing the role of people, training, and trust in successful implementation.

From scientific classifications to industrial functions

Empirical models start from observed relationships in data. They are efficient within the range of the available information and are useful when the main objective is description or interpolation. Mechanistic models start from biological principles such as maintenance, nutrient partitioning, intake regulation, heat exchange, and growth. Their value is not only predictive but explanatory, because they help the user understand why a response occurs and support more cautious extrapolation than purely correlative models.

In poultry practice, however, the distinction is not absolute. Fisher (2015) noted that the boundary between empirical and mechanistic models is "at best blurred," especially

when models are assembled to describe practical production systems. He also observed that many nutrient studies are still interpreted as numerical requirement statements, even though the more logical commercial interpretation is economic. That point is central for industry. Once a response is known, the question is no longer only what the requirement might be, but which feeding or management decision creates the best technical, economic, or sustainability outcome.

A model used in industry is therefore judged by more than its scientific label. It must be relevant to a decision, fast enough for commercial use, open to local calibration, connected to economic and sustainability targets, and simple enough to support adoption by technical teams and customers. This does not replace the scientific classifications proposed by France and Thornley (1984) or the broader framework discussed by Fisher (2015). Rather, it adds the implementation view needed when models move from research into routine business use. Once models are judged by their function in practice, the next question is why industry uses them.

Why industry uses models

Industry uses models because poultry production requires frequent decisions under biological and market uncertainty. One immediate use is technical monitoring of flock performance, where expected trajectories for body weight, feed intake, feed conversion ratio, mortality, and other key outputs provide a reference for identifying deviations and supporting diagnosis. The broader value is decision support. Biologically based simulation models, including digital twin-type applications, can integrate the main drivers of bird performance into a predicted outcome. Feed composition, ingredient quality, nutrient density, environment, management, growth potential, market objectives, and real production data can be used as inputs to evaluate the expected consequence of a decision before it is applied in the field.

This integration helps reduce uncertainty in volatile markets. Ingredient prices, feed costs, meat prices, target weights, and customer requirements change constantly, and the best biological response is not always the best commercial outcome. Models help

compare alternatives and clarify whether the objective should be performance, feed conversion, nutrient excretion, economic return, or a compromise among them. Models also create value for customers by translating biological knowledge into practical recommendations. They allow virtual experimentation through “what-if” scenarios, such as changing ingredients, adjusting lysine or energy, modifying feed phases, adopting seasonal programs, or changing target market weight. Testing all these options experimentally would require time, birds, facilities, and multiple flock cycles. Models make this exploration faster, more structured, and more useful for decision-making. These uses can be organized as a progression of capability, from static references to models that estimate responses and eventually select among alternative decisions.

Staircase of modeling progression

A practical way to describe current industrial implementation is as a staircase of modeling progression proposed by Ferguson (2024) (Figure 1). Each level adds decision relevance and potential value creation. Tables provide fixed references and support least-cost formulation. Requirement models add flexibility by linking nutrient needs to bird type, phase, or objective. Response models quantify how output changes when nutrition or management changes. Optimization models then search for the best solution once the response is known.

Staircase of Modeling Progression

From static tables to response models, optimization, and real-time sensor-enabled decision support. Hybrid and integrated models are shown as future directions, not current core steps.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the industrial staircase of modeling progression, adapted from Ferguson (2024), from tables to optimization, with hybrid and integrated models shown as future directions.

The staircase should not be interpreted as a replacement sequence. Tables remain useful when optimization models are available, and requirement models remain useful when response models exist. The staircase is better understood as a way to classify capability. This view is consistent with Fisher's (2015) argument that different modeling approaches can all have practical usefulness depending on the question being asked (Table 1). In industrial terms, the staircase reflects a broader shift from static requirement statements toward response interpretation and economic decision-making (Sakomura et al. 2019).

Table 1. Core industrial staircase of modeling progression for poultry-industry implementation.

Step	Main output	Typical industrial question	Main limitation / why the next step is needed
Tables	Fixed references and ingredient values	What is the ingredient value or static reference for formulation?	No direct animal response; limited support for scenario comparison.
Requirement models	Estimated nutrient need	What lysine or energy level is required for a bird, phase, or target?	Usually provides one target per scenario and limited guidance on trade-offs.
Response models	Predicted biological response	What happens if I change diet, season, stocking density, or management?	A decision rule is still needed to choose among alternative responses.
Optimization models	Best solution for a defined objective	Which scenario should I implement for feed conversion, body weight, profit, or nutrient excretion?	Needs reliable response model, calibration, and explicit objectives or constraints.

In this paper, the staircase is deliberately limited to the levels that are already most relevant for routine industrial implementation. Two additional directions are increasingly discussed beyond that point. Hybrid modeling is used here cautiously to describe a biological response model connected to AI-based tools for tasks such as data interpretation, anomaly detection, calibration support, user guidance, or automation logic. Integrated modeling refers to a more connected end-state in which biological models interact with barn data, feed mill information, logistics, and market signals inside a broader operational system. Conceptually, this direction overlaps with Fisher's (2015) category of real-time control models and with broader integrated management visions. Both directions are promising, but well-documented successful field cases remain limited. At the same time, the discussion of hybrid and integrated systems has become more relevant because of the current AI wave in agriculture.

The AI wave in poultry industry

The current AI wave has accelerated the modeling discussion because poultry systems now generate large and heterogeneous data streams from environmental controllers, feed systems, water meters, scales, cameras, microphones, laboratory analyses, and enterprise databases. Reviews of smart poultry management and precision livestock farming show that these data streams create new opportunities for

automation, early warning, welfare assessment, environment control, and forecasting (Norton et al. 2019; Neethirajan 2020).

The advantages of AI are clear. It can process data volumes that exceed manual interpretation, learn nonlinear relationships, detect abnormal patterns, and transform images, sounds, or sensor streams into near real-time alerts. In poultry systems, AI is especially attractive when the useful signal is embedded in complex data streams rather than in a small set of manually entered variables. In this role, AI can become a powerful layer for monitoring and interpretation around a biological model.

However, AI also has important limitations. It depends on real data, and those data must be representative, reliable, and well governed. If sensors drift, labels are poor, management conditions change, or data pipelines differ across farms, performance can decline quickly. Data-driven models also tend to interpolate better than they extrapolate to new genetics, climates, diets, or management systems. Many poultry houses are not yet instrumented well enough, and even high-technology houses still need more robust sensors, better interoperability, and higher-quality data before their outputs can be used confidently in growth and response models (Neethirajan and Kemp 2021). Finally, when AI outputs are difficult to interpret biologically, accountability becomes weaker and troubleshooting becomes harder.

A future AI layer may be able to evaluate data quality, connect reliable signals to a biological model, and generate trustworthy recommendations. Initiatives from start-ups and large companies suggest that this direction is plausible. For now, AI should be treated as an enabling capability to be integrated with biological models, not as a standalone replacement for biological understanding. This interpretation is consistent with recent reviews emphasizing that data-driven methods can improve forecasting and pattern recognition, while hybridization with mechanistic models helps preserve biological interpretation, decision support, and model transparency (Ellis et al. 2020; Leishman et al. 2023). The next implementation challenge is therefore not only digital, but also human.

People at the center of successful model implementation

Successful implementation of modeling is, above all, a human process. A model may be biologically sound and statistically accurate, yet still fail in practice if users cannot understand its assumptions or translate its outputs into daily decisions. For that reason, implementation should not end with the delivery of software, a report, or a technical presentation. It should begin with training and continue through local coaching, technical support, and practical guidance until users reach enough maturity to interpret results critically, recognize the limits of the tool, calibrate it when needed, and use it with confidence in their own production context. Trust is built through knowledge. As users understand how a model works and where it creates value, the model becomes part of routine decision-making rather than an external recommendation.

Part of this challenge begins much earlier, during professional training. Many animal-science programs provide a strong foundation in biochemistry and classical nutrition, which remains essential, but give less systematic attention to systems thinking, scenario analysis, and biological modeling. As a result, students may graduate with strong discipline-specific knowledge but limited preparation for a production system in which biology, management, environment, economics, and uncertainty interact continuously. Adding biological modeling, including growth and production modeling, to university training would not replace core disciplines. It would complement them by helping future nutritionists connect the different parts of the production system and propose changes that generate practical value across the chain, from farmer to consumer.

It is also important to clarify that biological modeling, especially response modeling, is not primarily a mathematical exercise, even though mathematics is the language used to express it. The main challenge lies in representing biology with enough realism to be useful. Eventually, a good model must describe how the bird grows/produce, how nutrients are partitioned, how feed intake is regulated, how heat is produced and dissipated, and how the bird interacts with feed, management, and

environment within a complex production system. Mathematics organizes these relationships into a formal structure, but the credibility of the model depends first on the quality of the biological representation. This distinction is important because modeling is often perceived as a field reserved for “math” specialists. In practice, the successful implementation of poultry models depends strongly on animal physiology, production biology, and whole-system understanding. Presenting poultry models in this way may help students and professionals see modeling as an accessible topic in poultry nutrition and as a relevant part of their work.

Conclusion

Successful model implementation in the poultry industry depends on making model value clear and usable. Scientific labels such as empirical or mechanistic remain useful, but industrial relevance is determined by the decision a model can support, the boundaries within which it should be used, and the confidence it provides under commercial conditions. The staircase of modeling progression contributes by positioning models according to their capability. It helps clarify what a model can deliver and how it may evolve as biological knowledge, data infrastructure, and digital tools improve. Hybrid and integrated systems are promising future directions, particularly with advances in AI, sensors, and farm connectivity. Their practical success, however, will depend on reliable data, biological interpretation, and validated decision rules. Until these conditions are consistently achieved, the priority should be to strengthen models that already support industry decisions while preparing for more connected systems. Across this process, people remain central. Models create value when users have enough knowledge and confidence to translate outputs into sound decisions. This returns to the challenge introduced at the beginning of the text. Poultry decisions are repeated, complex, and often too urgent to wait for multiple experimental cycles. Modeling becomes successful when it helps the industry act faster, with better structure and enough confidence to move from prediction to decision.

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13. Application of models to develop feeding programs for broiler chickens laying hens and broiler breeders

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Abstract

Traditional empirical dose–response approaches, although practical, are limited to specific experimental conditions and have restricted applicability under variations in genetic strain, environment, and age. Accurately determining nutrient requirements based on animal performance and environmental conditions is essential for developing feeding strategies that optimize resource use, enhance productivity, and improve sustainability in poultry production. This review highlights the use of dynamic factorial models to predict energy and amino acid requirements in poultry. These models integrate biological parameters such as growth and tissue deposition into nutrient utilization frameworks for feeding program applications. Models are presented for broiler chickens, laying hens, and broiler breeders, based on biological assays developed over two decades at UNESP Jaboticabal Brasil. The modeling approach is based on growth potential described by the Gompertz function for protein deposition, combined with allometric relationships between body protein and other components (lipid, ash, and water) to estimate tissue deposition rates. Body composition was determined using in vivo methods such as dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry and indirect calorimetry. Factorial models incorporate dynamic

growth and production outputs (body weight gain, egg mass, and protein and lipid deposition) to partition nutrient requirements into maintenance, growth, and reproduction. Energy models are adjusted for environmental temperature, while amino acid models consider utilization efficiency. These models provide robust tools for estimating nutrient requirements and support feeding programs tailored to specific production conditions.

Keywords: Broiler breeder, broiler chickens, factorial models, laying hens, nutritional program.

Introduction

Many studies have focused on determining the optimal balance of essential amino acids and energy requirements for poultry were conducted through doses-response trials using empirical models to estimate nutrient requirements. However, these models are limited by the specific condition under which the data was collected, making them less suitable for broader application. To improve accuracy, more comprehensive factorial models have been developed, accounting for factors such as body weight (BW), chemical components (protein, fat and mineral), and growth rates. These models are more feasible, predicting energy and amino acid needs across various ages, genetic strain, and environments. As was proposed by the National Research Council's (2012) for swine, this material encourages the use of factorial models in poultry nutrition. Studies conducted at UNESP-Jaboticabal, Brazil, over two decades aimed at developing models to predict the energy and amino acid requirements of broiler chickens, laying hens and broiler breeders.

Describing poultry growth

Birds are continuously growing, changing their chemical composition, and geneticists are constantly modifying genotypes, requiring of a continuous nutritional requirement updating. To overcome these challenges, Emmans (1987) proposed the genetic growth potential theory to describe the body components changes along the age of the birds. They introduced the Gompertz function to describe protein growth, a key

factor in predicting nutritional requirements. This model allows for the prediction of growth by focusing on chemical components such as protein, lipid, ash, and water. The use of Dual Energy X-Ray Absorptiometry (DXA) in studies conducted at FCAV/UNESP enabled non-destructive measurements body composition over time of broiler (Gonçalves et al., 2020) and laying pullet (Alves et al., 2019). Based on these results the protein growth models for each poultry category and strains were developed (Table 1).

Table 1. Body protein (BP) growth curve of broiler chickens and laying hens.

Poultry category - Strain	Model (BP – kg)
Broiler chickens (Cobb 500 male)	$BP=1.296 \times \text{EXP}(-\text{EXP}(-0.048 \times (\text{Age}-42)))$
Laying pullets (Dekalb brown)	$BP=0.303 \times \text{EXP}(-\text{EXP}(-0.027 \times (\text{Age}-52)))$

BP: Body protein. Age in days. Sources: Gonçalves et al., (2019), Alves et al., (2018)

From the above body protein prediction, the weights of body lipid, ash, and water were estimated allometrically based on the body protein weight. After that, the principal components of body protein (BP), protein deposition (PD) and lipid deposition (LD) were estimated and used as inputs in the factorial models to estimate the energy and amino acids requirements.

Modelling energy utilization in poultry

Metabolizable energy (ME) is widely used in poultry nutrition to estimate energy requirements through factorial models, where ME intake is allocated for maintenance, growth, and production. Energy retention (ER) is influenced by the efficiency of energy utilization for maintenance (km) and growth (kg), with a linear model used to describe this relationship. Further partitioning of energy shows different efficiencies for protein (kp) and lipid (kl) deposition, with lipid being more efficient.

Energy requirements for maintenance

Factors affecting MEm include age, body composition, growth stage, and environmental conditions like temperature and feather cover. Studies at FCAV/UNESP used comparative slaughter techniques to estimate MEm in various poultry strains,

considering temperature and genotype effects. Maintenance energy (MEM) was calculated based on the energy retained equal to zero where is not shown gain or loss of body weight.

Temperature effect on energy for maintenance

Environmental temperature significantly affects maintenance energy, as birds increase energy intake to regulate body temperature in extreme conditions. Critical temperature (CT) defines the point where environmental temperature begins to affect energy needs. The correction of MEM by the environmental temperature were developed by Neme et al., (2005) as $MEM=92.4+6.73\times(CT-T_{env})$ for $T_{env}<CT$, and $MEM=92.4+0.08\times(T_{env}-CT)$ for $T_{env}>CT$.

Energy utilization for growth

The FCAV/UNESP studies used multiple regression analyses to determine *kp* and *kfat* in pullets and broilers. These efficiencies were applied to calculate the ME required to deposit one gram of protein (12.3 kcal/g) or lipid (13.5 kcal/g) by Sakomura et al., (2003) and Longo et al., (2006).

Energy utilization for egg production

Once hens begin laying eggs, energy allocation shifts significantly, with minimal energy directed toward growth and the majority used for egg production. The energy required for egg production is primarily a function of the egg mass produced. Studies conducted at FCAV/UNESP determined that the energy content of eggs is 1.54 kcal/g for broiler breeders and 1.49 kcal/g for laying hens (Rabello, 2006; Sakomura et al., 2005). The efficiency of metabolizable energy (ME) utilization for egg production was 64% for broiler breeders and 62% for laying hens, resulting in an ME requirement of 2.40 kcal/g of eggs for both hens.

Models to estimate the requirement of metabolizable energy

Factorial models were developed to predict MEm based on metabolic body weight, temperature, and protein/lipid deposition, while separate models estimate energy needs for growth and egg production. These models help optimize poultry diets by accurately predicting energy requirements across different conditions genotype (Table 2).

Table 2. Factorial models to estimate metabolize energy requirements for poultry.

Models for growing poultry	
Temperature above CT	Temperature below CT
<i>Broiler breeder pullets</i>	
$ME = BW^{0.75} \times 144 + 0.88 \times (T - CT) + 13.5 \times LD + 12.3 \times PD$	$BW^{0.75} \times 144 + 6.73 \times (CT - T) + 13.5 \times LD + 12.3 \times PD$
<i>Egg-laying type pullets</i>	
$ME = BW^{0.75} \times 92.4 + 0.88 \times (T - CT) + 13.5 \times LD + 12.3 \times PD$	$BW^{0.75} \times 92.4 + 6.73 \times (CT - T) + 13.5 \times LD + 12.3 \times PD$
<i>Broilers</i>	
$ME = BW^{0.75} \times 112 + 0.88 \times (T - CT) + 13.5 \times LD + 12.3 \times PD$	$BW^{0.75} \times 112 + 6.73 \times (CT - T) + 13.5 \times LD + 12.3 \times PD$
Models for breeders and laying hens	
<i>Broiler breeder</i>	
$ME = BW^{0.75} \times 113 + 0.88 \times (T - CT) + 7.62 \times BWG + 2.40 \times EM$	$BW^{0.75} \times (113 + 6.73 \times (CT - T)) + 7.62 \times BWG + 2.40 \times EM$
<i>Laying hen</i>	
$ME = BW^{0.75} \times 112 + 0.88 \times (T - CT) + 6.68 \times BWG + 2.40 \times EM$	$BW^{0.75} \times (112 + 6.73 \times (CT - T)) + 6.68 \times BWG + 2.40 \times EM$

BW: Body weight, CT: Critical temperature, BWG: Body weight gain, EM: Egg mass, LD: Lipid deposition, PD: protein deposition. Sources: Sakomura et al., (2010), Sakomura (2004), Sakomura et al., (2005), Neme et al., (2005), Rabello et al., (2006).

Models to estimate amino acids for poultry

Amino acid requirements are estimated through factorial models, which partition the needs into maintenance and growth and production components. These models consider both the deposition of amino acids into body protein and the efficiency of utilization. Studies were developed to estimate the requirement for principal amino acids: Lys, Met+Cys, Thr, Val, Iso, and Trp.

Amino acid requirement for maintenance

In order to establish the maintenance requirements for Lys, Met+Cys, Thr, Val, Trp, and Ile, experiments were conducted at UNESP-Jaboticabal, using adult cockerels fed increasing intakes of a diet limiting in the amino acid under study (Bonato et al., 2011; Sakomura et al., 2015). Nitrogen retention was regressed against the amount of amino

acid consumed, and the maintenance requirement for each amino acid was regarded as the amount of that amino acid required to balance nitrogen intake and retention. Maintenance requirements for amino acids are showed in table 3.

Table 3. Lysine, Met+Cys, threonine, valine, isoleucine, and tryptophan requirements for maintenance, expressed in different units.

Amino acid	mg/kg BW	mg/kg BW ^{0.75}	mg/kg BP ^{0.73,u}
Lysine	32	45	151
Met+Cys	19	26	87
Threonine	17	22	76
Valine	41	59	247
Isoleucine	20	32	134
Tryptophan	5	9	37

BW, body weight; BP, body protein weight; *u*, degree of maturity = BP_t/BP_m = 1.

Efficiency of amino acid utilization

The efficiency of absorbed amino acids being incorporated into body protein is typically assumed a linear relationship between amino acid intake above maintenance and retention, with the efficiency represented by the slope of this linear function. Different amino acids are utilized with varying efficiencies due to their distinct metabolic roles. Lys, for instance, is highly efficient for protein synthesis, while sulfur amino acids like Met have lower retention due to their roles in methylation and sulfur donation. Additionally, factors like health status can affect the efficiency of amino acids such as Thr, Trp, and Val, as they play a crucial role in immune responses. Six dose response trials were conducted in studies at UNESP-Jaboticabal, Brazil to determine the efficiency of amino acids in broilers. The requirement for growth was determined considering the amino acid deposition and efficiency.

Factorial models to predict amino acid requirements for broilers

A factorial model developed to estimate amino acid requirements in broilers was based on BP, amino acid deposition expressed as PD and efficiency of utilization for growth. Additionally, it was considered the accounts for body and feather protein (FP) separately, excluding lipid deposition. It partitions amino acid requirements for

maintenance and growth into feather-free body and feathers, using the body protein content and degree of maturity (Table 3).

Table 3. Models to estimate the amino acid requirement for broiler chickens

Amino acid (mg/d)		Maintenance		Growth
Lysine	=	$(151 \times BP^{0.73} \times u) + (0.01 \times FP \times 18)$	+	$(75 \times PD + 18 \times FPD) / 0.77$
Met+Cys	=	$(87 \times BP^{0.73} \times u) + (0.01 \times FP \times 76)$	+	$(36 \times PD + 76 \times FPD) / 0.78$
Threonine	=	$(76 \times BP^{0.73} \times u) + (0.01 \times FP \times 44)$	+	$(42 \times PD + 44 \times FPD) / 0.73$
Valine	=	$(247 \times BP^{0.73} \times u) + (0.01 \times FP \times 60)$	+	$(44 \times PD + 60 \times FPD) / 0.73$
Isoleucine	=	$(134 \times BP^{0.73} \times u) + (0.01 \times FP \times 44)$	+	$(37 \times PD + 44 \times FPD) / 0.69$
Tryptophan	=	$(37 \times BP^{0.73} \times u) + (0.01 \times FP \times 5.4)$	+	$(11 \times PD + 5.4 \times FPD) / 0.71$

BP: Body protein, FP: Feather protein, PD: Protein deposition, FPD: Feather protein deposition, u: Maturity degree.

Models to estimate amino acid requirements for laying-type pullets were developed similarly to those for broilers. Maintenance coefficients and efficiencies for lysine (0.76), methionine cysteine (0.71), and threonine (0.86) were derived from dose-response assays. During growth, the primary focus is on BP and PD in the body and feathers. However, around 21 days before laying, amino acids are also needed for reproductive organ development, particularly in the ovary and oviduct. The models account for these additional requirements using protein deposition rates in reproductive tissues. Prior to 14-old-weeks, models exclude reproductive development (Table 4).

Table 4. Models to estimate the amino acid requirement for laying pullets.

Amino acid (mg/d)		Maintenance		Growth		Reproductive organs†
Lysine	=	$(151 \times BP^{0.73} \times u) + (0.01 \times FP \times 18)$	+	$(75 \times PD + 18 \times FPD) / 0.76$	+	$(75 \times OvaPD + 75 \times OviPD) / 0.76$
Met+Cys	=	$(87 \times BP^{0.73} \times u) + (0.01 \times FP \times 89)$	+	$(34 \times PD + 89 \times FPD) / 0.71$	+	$(34 \times OvaPD + 34 \times OviPD) / 0.71$
Threonine	=	$(76 \times BP^{0.73} \times u) + (0.01 \times FP \times 44)$	+	$(42 \times PD + 44 \times FPD) / 0.86$	+	$(42 \times OvaPD + 42 \times OviPD) / 0.86$

BP: Body protein, FP: Feather protein, PD: Protein deposition, FPD: Feather protein deposition, u: Maturity degree.

For laying hens and broiler breeders, the models developed were based on Reading model (Fisher et al., 1973). This model considers that the response of each individual is described as an ascending straight-line followed by a plateau, represented by a linear broken-line model. Since individuals differ with respect to their body weight and their breakpoint, i.e. their genetic potential output, the response of the population is curvilinear (Curnow, 1973). Considering this population variation to estimate amino acid intake, the model is classified as a stochastic model. The advantage of such a model

is that it enables the calculation of the optimum economic intake of each amino acid based on the marginal cost of the amino acid and the marginal revenue for eggs. Based on this approach, trials were conducted at FCAV/UNESP with laying hens and broiler breeders to estimate the parameters for each amino acid in the egg-laying phase provided in table 5.

Application of the models

This presentation demonstrates how the described models can estimate nutrient requirements for different poultry genotypes. The factorial models were applied to predict daily requirements for energy and essential amino acids across various growth stages, or egg production period, assessing feasibility to develop nutritional program more accurately, as demonstrated in figure 1.

Table 5. Reading Model parameters from studies conducted at FCAV/UNESP.

Parameters	Amino acids					
	Lys	Met+Cys	Thr	Val	Ile	Trp
<i>Laying hens</i>						
EO _{max} (g/day)	60.0	64.0	64.0	59.0	59.0	59.0
BW (kg)	1.53	1.53	1.53	1.35	1.35	1.35
a (mg/kg of egg mass)	10.7	7.96	6.73	9.83	7.23	2.28
b ¹ (mg/kg)	32.3	19.0	17.0	41.0	20.0	5.00
σEO _{max}	6.04	10.0	10.0	15.0	15.0	15.0
σBW	0.15	0.12	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.13
<i>Broiler breeders</i>						
EO _{max} (g/day)	50.0	-	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.0
BW (kg)	4.00	-	4.00	3.50	3.50	3.50
a (mg/day)	14.5	-	9.50	12.0	9.91	3.10
b (mg/kg)	32.0	-	17.0	41.0	20.0	5.00
σEO _{max}	12.5	-	12.5	10.0	10.0	10.0
σBW	0.35	-	0.30	0.35	0.35	0.35

¹Determined in adult cockerels; expressed in mg/kg BW for Lys, Met+Cys, Thr, and Trp. Sakomura and Rostagno (2016)

Feeding programs for broilers, pullets, and laying hens were also developed to optimize amino acid intake based on growth and egg production and illustrating the practical application of these models for the poultry industry.

Figure 1. Daily lysine requirements calculated using the factorial model (---) and a three-phase nutritional program (-) developed considering the midpoint requirement for each phase for white egg replacement pullets.

These models can be used to elaborate nutritional tables, as illustrated in table 6. The easy application of this model was developing a computational program available online (www.poultrymodel.com), based on the theories and models here mentioned.

Table 6. Nutritional Requirements of White Replacement Pullets, According to Growing Phase (%)

Phase		Starter		Grower/Developer		Pre Lay	
Age (Weeks)		1-4		5-10		11-15	
		16-18					
Average Weight	kg	0.114		0.514		1.001	
Gain	g/day	7.4		13.4		10.3	
SID Lysine	g/day	0.176		0.322		0.323	
Metabolizable Energy	kcal/day	59		129		159	
Net Energy	kcal/day	43		96		124	
Diet Metab Energy	kcal/kg	2.900		2.900		2.900	
Diet Net Energy	kcal/kg	2.086		2.163		2.253	
Intake	g/day	20.3		44.6		55.0	
Nutrients							
Total Crude Protein	%	15.95		13.41		10.91	
Digestible Protein	%	14.36		12.04		9.76	
Calcium	%	1.144		0.954		0.764	
Available Phosphorus	%	0.419		0.357		0.299	
Digestible	%	0.355		0.303		0.253	
Phosphorus							0.510
Potassium	%	0.528		0.521		0.511	
Sodium	%	0.182		0.169		0.160	
Chlorine	%	0.159		0.151		0.150	
Linoleic Acid	%	1.028		1.000		1.000	
Amino Acids		SID	Total	SID	Total	SID	Total
Lysine	%	0.866	0.962	0.722	0.802	0.588	0.764
Methionine	%	0.355	0.394	0.317	0.353	0.258	0.352
Met + Cys	%	0.641	0.712	0.570	0.634	0.465	0.634
Threonine	%	0.615	0.683	0.484	0.561	0.394	0.535
Tryptophan	%	0.156	0.173	0.152	0.168	0.123	0.160
Arginine	%	0.918	1.020	0.787	0.874	0.641	0.833
Gly + Ser	%	1.126	1.251	0.830	0.962	0.676	0.848
Valine	%	0.684	0.760	0.570	0.642	0.465	0.634
Isoleucine	%	0.615	0.684	0.534	0.602	0.435	0.581
Leucine	%	0.970	1.077	0.859	0.946	0.700	0.993
Histidine	%	0.320	0.356	0.267	0.297	0.218	0.298
Phenylalanine	%	0.580	0.635	0.498	0.553	0.406	0.542
Phee + Tyr	%	1.048	1.164	0.909	1.011	0.741	0.986
Essential Nitrogen	%	1.149	1.276	0.963	1.073	0.781	1.039

Source: Brazilian Tables (Rostagno et al., (2024)

Conclusion

Integrating factorial models into poultry nutrition represents a paradigm shift from traditional empirical approaches, offering precision in quantifying energy and amino acid requirements tailored to genetic potential, production objectives, and environmental conditions. Models proposed for energy requirement are explored at

both levels, at metabolizable and at net energy, also considering the principal factors that influence energy requirement. Additionally, for amino acid requirements, two models were proposed, based on performance response (easy applicability) and body composition (more precise), that can be employed for feeding program development. All models start with parameter estimation, with strong biological interpretations that make the model more confident, interpretable, and flexible.

This review synthesizes two decades of research at UNESP, demonstrating that models grounded in biological principles provide robust frameworks for predicting nutrient requirements across broilers, laying hens, and broiler breeders. In addition, the models presented in this review, along with the online platform on which all models were implemented, can help nutritionists develop dynamic nutritional programs tailored to each line's genetic performance, ambient temperature, and management practices, thereby optimizing productivity. Implementing models developed with robust predictive parameters and based on a consistent theory, the models proposed here represent, when complemented with the online tool, an important contribution to the adoption of modelling in practical poultry nutrition.

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14. Integrating net energy of feed with animal utilization: the Lavinesp NE Model

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Abstract

The classical feed formulation is based on two main components: the animal and the feed. Precision on the feed formulation and optimization is based on trying to reduce the differences between "what the animal needs, considering their intrinsic and extrinsic factors" and "what is available on the feed, considering their characteristics and composition". Each component faces different challenges. For example, animal characteristics show variability across genetic, sex, age, and environmental-social conditions (e.g., density, temperature). Feed factor also shows significant variability in its composition due to both traditional and non-traditional physico-chemical characteristics. Computational determination of both conditions simultaneously can be a "fast-easy-practical" way to implement modeling in continuous feed formulation. Based on mechanistic models to determine energy and amino acid requirements, and the application of NE equations to calculate the energy value of feedstuffs, we aim to implement software that automatically determines both factors (requirements and feed values) based on the net energy system.

Keywords: Energy requirements, energy value, feed formulator, modelling,

Introduction

Practical poultry feed formulation is based on a least-cost linear programming approach, in which ingredients are included based on their energy and nutrient compositions to meet the animal's requirements. In this sense, current feed formulation is composed of the feed characteristic, described by its energy and nutritional content (digestible amino acids), and the animal characteristic, represented by the average of the population, which varies according to its intrinsic and extrinsic characteristics. An optimal feed formulation consists of finding a "match" between the feed value and animal requirement. That means the minimum difference between what the feed supplies and what the animal uses.

Mechanistic modeling based on growth potential helps develop simulations that account for animal characteristics and the social-physical factors that influence growth. With that, we can describe the growth of animals based on their components (tissue deposition, heat production, and excretion) and also the efficiency of nutrients and energy utilization. Through that, researchers and nutritionists can simulate real-life conditions to make better decisions, taking production factors into account and moving closer to an overall response. The models developed are based on the net energy system, as they propose that this system represents a more closed system that better reflects the animal response.

The objective is to demonstrate the application and development of computational software based on the net energy system and modeling approach for practical poultry nutrition.

Figure 1. LAVINESP #NE Model, an integrative and complementary approach of animal requirement with the feed value for poultry.

Conceptual basis of the model

The model is based on the growth potential to determine the animal's requirements and on the energy value of feeds. Requirements are based on a set of functions to correct the energy requirements considering the physical and social factors of the production (as described in previous chapters).

Figure 2. Flow-chart of the conceptual model of #NE Lavinesp.

Inputs of the model

The model works with essential inputs included in the model run (Figure 1). Even more information is required to describe growth potential, depending on genetic strain and sex, because growth patterns differ between males and females.

This material was developed by:
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General information	
Code	
Client	
Company	

Animal specifications	
Bird category	Broiler
Strain	Cobb 500
Sex	Male

#NE FORMULATOR

building the future of poultry

Production conditions	
Light program h of light	16
Sanitary condition index	

Feeding phases	
Initial age d	1
Final age d	8
Phases	Start

Initial condition	
Initial BW g	44
Initial Protein g	6

Environmental program					
Initial age (d)	Final Age (d)	Temperature (°C)	RH (%)	Air velocity (m/s2)	Density (birds/m2)
1	2	33.0	50.0	2.0	28
2	3	32.5	50.0	2.0	28
3	4	32.0	50.0	2.0	28
4	5	31.5	50.0	2.0	28
5	6	31.0	50.0	2.0	28
6	7	30.5	50.0	2.0	28
7	8	30.0	50.0	2.0	28

Feeding Program											
Initial age	Final Age	AMEn (kcal/kg)	NE (kcal/kg)	CP (%)	dCP (%)	EE (%)	DM (%)	WHC (g water/g)	SID Lys (%)	SID Me	
1	8	2950	2331	25.31	22.89	4	90	2	1.37	0.55	
9	17	3000	2375	24.70	22.34	7	90	2	1.34	0.54	
18	27	3050	2400	23.06	20.84	8	90	2.4	1.26	0.53	
28	35	3100	2450	22.07	19.95	9	90	2.6	1.202	0.51	
36	43	3150	2470	21.2	19.17	10	90	2.6	1.171	0.502	
44	56	3200	2530	20.59	18.81	11	90	2.6	1.137	0.488	

Figure 3. Inputs required to model processing.

Together with initial BW and body protein weight (which can be calculated as a direct relationship with initial BW), the first step in describing the growth potential of the birds is. In addition to showing the variation in growth due to feed energy and nutritional composition, dietary composition should be reported for each feeding phase, including AMEn, CP, EE, DM, and digestible amino acid composition. With this information, the dietary effect on growth is elucidated.

To understand the effects of different social and environmental conditions, customers should describe their environment (temperature, air velocity, stocking density) and the main factors that influence energy requirements and feed intake regulation.

Influence of the factors in protein deposition and feed intake

Depending on the limiting effects of the factors (nutritional and environmental), these factors directly influence PD. If the feeding program provides an adequate amount of energy, amino acids, and protein, it directly influences growth potential, allowing the limiting effect to be observed dynamically. As a result, animals can intake sufficient feed to meet their requirements; however, external factors (environmental temperature) and gut capacity can represent the physical limits of feed intake, resulting in the "actual" feed intake.

Figure 3. Influence of the factors in the protein deposition and feed intake on broiler chickens.

Depending on the limiting effects of the factors (nutritional and environmental), these factors directly influence PD. If the feeding program provides an adequate amount of energy, amino acids, and protein, it directly influences growth potential, allowing the limiting effect to be observed dynamically (Figure 3).

As a result, animals can intake sufficient feed to meet their requirements; however, external factors (environmental temperature) and gut capacity can represent the physical limits of feed intake, resulting in the "actual" feed intake.

Application and comparison with classical feeding program

With adequate input information and cautious result interpretation, a nutritionist can develop a customized feed formulation program based on nutritional and economic

evaluations. In an example developed according to the classical Brazilian Tables (2024) recommendations, the model recommended a different feeding program, recalculating the energy and nutritional recommendations (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Energy and digestible lysine recommendations are compared with genetic guideline for male broiler chickens.

Additional nitrogen utilization aims at nutritional decision-making and the reduction of CT in CP and environmental impact solutions (Figure 5). With the computational tool, it will be possible to make decisions through simple simulations that compare with their actual nutritional recommendations, and to develop strategies to support future changes based on nutrition, economic factors, and environmental sustainability.

Figure 5. Dynamic representation of the nitrogen utilization of broiler chickens based on a simulation approach.

Application in feed formulation

The optimization procedure is integrated with the model, allowing the nutritionist to adapt their feed formulation for each feeding phase and manually select an optimized formula. For that, a feed formulator based on two criteria (least-cost and meet requirement) based on a linear solution is integrated into the model (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Interface of feed formulator based on net energy system.

This formulation includes different equators of the net system (for broiler chickens and laying hens) and can be applied to individual diets. The feedstuff dataset also includes the calculated NE values for raw materials, based on Brazilian tables.

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15. Nutritional modeling for sustainable poultry production

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Introduction

Although poultry is among the least environmentally impactful animal protein sources, the projected global demand for poultry products is a growing environmental concern. Manure-derived nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) are important elements of soil health and sustainability of crop production. Nevertheless, in area of intensive animal production, N and P losses contribute to severe eutrophication, acidification, and greenhouse gas emissions (Van Zenten et al., 2019). Phosphate is a limited and non-renewable resource produced by only few countries, making it a strategically critical factor in global food production (Brownlie et al., 2023). Therefore, improving the efficiency of using N and P in the food system is crucial and requires a holistic, system-level approach. Mathematical modelling is particularly well suited to this task, as it provides a structured and cost-effective way to understand, predict, and optimize complex systems (Emmans, 1981).

How to optimize the use of Nitrogen and Phosphorus in birds

Optimizing the use of N and P relies on precise and robust formulation system that includes precise estimation of feedstuff values and of requirements. Today the most

accurate method for assessing the nutrient values of feed ingredients is ileal digestible content (Rodehutscord et al., 2013; Rostagno, 2024). Nevertheless, those methods provide a fixed value per ingredient and do not consider the modulating factors. To overcome that, empirical modeling through meta-analysis allows predicting digestibility considering the most important factors, namely Ca and phytate P in broilers (Mariani et al., 2026) and interaction between AA (Zouaoui et al., 2021). Mechanistic modelling can also help quantify and rank the modulating factors as performed in laying hen for dietary Ca and P fate (Hervo et al., 2026). The factorial modelling approach that sums up the requirement for maintenance, growth and production is the most precise method. Model predicting growth of soft tissue and bone and the fate of AA (Reis et al., 2023a) and Ca and P (Reis et al., 2023b) have been developed and used to predict requirements. A key innovation of this model is the dynamic Ca:P ratio and its multicriteria output showing tradeoff between growth performance and bone mineralization. Validation trials are currently ongoing.

It is worth noting that although we have precise formulation system, we must try to fit the dynamic evolution of requirements over time. For that, we can use multiple feeding phase, up to 4 phases are currently used in many countries, but this still results in excess for most of the time. Méda et al. (2019, 2022) recently proposed a modeling approach for the implementation of precision feeding strategies mixing two different diets and distributed to the birds. Feeding strategies can also be implemented to improve N and P utilization such as lowering crude protein (e.g., Alfonso-Avila et al., 2018; de Rauglaudre et al., 2023; de Rauglaudre et al., 2025), using phytase by considering the modulating factors to design precise P and Ca matrix, and depletion-repletion (Rousseau et al., 2016; Omotoso et al., 2023). Those compensatory mechanisms are well known for laying hens that change its capacity of absorption during the day (Sinclair-Black et al., 2023) and must be integrated in the future in the mechanistic models in both broilers and laying hens.

Conclusions and perspectives

Robust models have been developed to predict bird response to P and N and requirements but can also be used to predict excretion. About 20-30% of the environmental impact comes from manure management (Andretta et al., 2021). Therefore, another key strategy to reduce the environmental impacts of poultry production is to ensure better use of slurry as a fertilizer. Life cycle analysis allows evaluating the environmental footprint of a product and can be used to identify and test strategies to reduce environmental footprint. For the moment it lacks precision due to inaccurate data and knowledge on the system. Nevertheless, there is improvement and data generation ongoing to improve this modeling method.

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16. Implementing Net Energy Systems: An Industry Roadmap

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Introduction

Feed commonly accounts for 70–80% of total production costs, and the increasing use of alternative ingredients has made accurate feed energy evaluation even more critical. In this context, poultry nutrition is moving toward a more precise integration of animal, feed, and environment interactions. This shift raises the question of whether metabolizable energy (ME) remains the most appropriate, or whether net energy (NE) should become the preferred system for future feed formulation.

Gross energy (GE), digestible energy (DE), ME, and NE represent successive refinements in the biological evaluation of feed energy. In poultry, ME has been widely used because urinary and fecal losses are excreted together, making ME practical and historically relevant. However, ME ignores heat increment, which varies according to nutrient type. This represents the main conceptual justification for moving from ME to NE. Recent reviews in pigs and poultry confirm that NE is the most physiologically meaningful system because it estimates the energy truly available to the animal after digestive and metabolic heat losses.

Why net energy differs from metabolizable energy

Gross energy (GE) represents the total energy released when the feed is burned in a bomb calorimeter; it is measured with a high accuracy (± 40 kJ/kg). If direct calorimetry data is unavailable, GE can be estimated using chemical composition-based equations (Noblet et al., 2022).

Apparent metabolizable energy (AME) is calculated by subtracting fecal, urinary, and gaseous energy losses from GE. In poultry, feces and urine are excreted together, making AME measurement more practical than digestible energy (DE); in addition, gaseous energy losses are negligible. True metabolizable energy (TME) accounts for endogenous losses but it is less and less used (NRC, 1994). Energy losses in urine as uric acid depend on dietary protein content and physiological stage (e.g., stage of growth, egg production). To standardize AME values, nitrogen (N) balance corrections are applied, resulting in the conventional and historical AME corrected for zero N retention (AMEn). However, in balanced broiler diets, N retention is ~60% of N intake (Cozannet et al., 2011; Wu et al., 2019; Tay-Zar et al., 2024). It is then preferable to standardize the AME values at such levels of N retention (AMEs; Noblet et al., 2022) for being representative of broiler metabolism and practical conditions. The following formula $AMEs = AMEn + 0.6 \times 34.36 \times N / 100$ with AMEs and AMEn as MJ/kg DM and N in feed as % of DM can be used for calculating AMEs according to a 60% efficiency for N utilization.

Net energy (NE) is derived from metabolizable energy (AME) by subtracting the heat increment (HI) from digestion, metabolism, and basic physical activity. NE reflects more accurately feed energy utilization than AME (Wu et al., 2019; Tay-Zar et al., 2024; Noblet et al., 2024). The NE content of a compound feed or an ingredient can be calculated from prediction equations involving the AMEs value and the fat, crude protein and dietary fiber levels in the feed, either compound feeds or ingredients (Noblet et al., 2024). Despite its advantages, NE systems are not yet widely used in poultry nutrition.

Measurement, prediction, and implementation constraints

In practice, NE is derived from calorimetry, most often indirect calorimetry, whereby heat production is estimated from oxygen consumption and carbon dioxide production (Brouwer, 1965; Noblet et al., 2022). This approach allows the partitioning of heat production into fasting heat production, the thermic effect of feeding, and

activity-related heat production. However, NE is not a pure feed trait unless animals and environmental sources of variation are tightly controlled. Bird activity, body weight, genotype, climate, housing, health status, feeding pattern, and methodological design all influence measured heat production (Noblet et al., 2022; Noblet, 2024). The primary industry challenge is therefore methodological: practical implementation requires standard operating procedures, well-defined biological models, and careful interpretation when comparing values generated under different experimental conditions. In addition, prediction equations can facilitate implementation only if they are built and validated on robust calorimetry datasets (Wu et al., 2019; Tay-Zar et al., 2024).

Following the work of Noblet et al. (2024), robust prediction equations combining AME with a limited number of routinely available chemical criteria appear promising for estimating the NE content of both feed ingredients and complete diets. One such equation proposed by Noblet et al. is:

$$NE = 0.804 \times AME_s - 0.026 \times CP + 0.015 \times Cfat - 0.018 \times NDF$$

where NE is expressed in MJ/kg DM, AME_s is apparent metabolizable energy standardized to 60% nitrogen retention (MJ/kg DM), CP is crude protein content (% DM), Cfat is crude fat content (% DM), and NDF is neutral detergent fiber content (% DM). This equation reflects the major determinants of the efficiency with which metabolizable energy is converted into net energy: AME_s provides the energetic basis, while the negative coefficients for CP and NDF account for the higher heat increment associated with protein metabolism and fiber utilization, respectively. Conversely, the positive coefficient for crude fat reflects the higher efficiency of fat energy deposition and its lower heat increment.

Such equations could make NE systems more operational in practice because they rely on measurements that are either already available in feed evaluation databases or can be routinely generated by feed laboratories. However, their practical implementation should remain anchored to high-quality calorimetry data and should

be systematically cross-validated using independent published datasets. This is essential to confirm their robustness, reproducibility, and applicability across diverse feed ingredients, complete diets, animal genotypes, ages, and experimental contexts (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Cross validation of NE prediction equation using data from the literature (Ning et al., 2014, Liu et al., 2017, 2022 & 2023).

Reformulation consequences for ingredient ranking and economics

The business case for NE depends on how formulation outcomes change under an NE system. Evidence from broiler studies indicates that NE can re-rank raw materials relative to ME (Carré et al., 2014; Wu et al., 2019). Protein-rich ingredients tend to lose value under NE system because their metabolic use is energetically less efficient, whereas some cereal ingredients or energy-dense ingredients may gain relative competitiveness. This has direct implications for shadow pricing, raw material substitutions, and least-cost formulation strategies. In commercial practice, NE may therefore reduce feed cost not because it increases nutrient supply, but because it values nutrients more realistically and better aligns ingredient choice with biological and metabolic efficiency (Wu et al., 2019; Noblet, 2024).

Net energy as an enabler of low-CP and precision nutrition strategies

A second key domain for NE implementation is the formulation of low-crude-protein (CP) diets. Reducing dietary CP is attractive for lowering feed cost variability and nitrogen excretion, however animal performance may deteriorate when amino acid balance, glycine supply, or the energy-to-amino-acid ratio is suboptimal (de Rauglaudre et al., 2023; Strifler et al., 2023). An NE framework is particularly relevant in this context because it accounts for the higher thermogenic cost associated with excess protein and may better interpret shifts in lean versus fat deposition when dietary protein is reduced (Carré et al., 2014; Wu et al., 2019). From an industry perspective, NE should therefore not be viewed simply as a replacement metric for ME, but rather as a nutritional system that supports more coherent and precise formulation when amino acid density, crude protein level, and energy supply are optimized simultaneously (Strifler et al., 2023; Noblet, 2024).

Why enzymes may show greater value under a NE framework

A third implementation domain concerns feed additives, with particular emphasis on enzymes. The presentation underpinning this paper emphasizes that enzyme responses may be more clearly expressed under an NE system than when evaluated using ME. This is biologically plausible, as NSP enzymes, proteases, and phytases can affect more than apparent digestibility: they can reduce endogenous nutrient losses, improve nutrient partitioning, mitigate anti-nutritional effects, and modify the heat increment associated with digestion and metabolism. If these mechanisms either reduce heat production or increase the proportion of retained energy, NE becomes a more sensitive and relevant descriptor of additive value than ME alone (Wu et al., 2019). For innovation teams, this creates an opportunity to re-evaluate feed additive portfolios using endpoints that are more closely aligned with animal efficiency and physiological impact of feed additives for broilers.

The next frontier: health, resilience, and dynamic energy use

A fourth frontier is the integration of NE with bird health and resilience. During inflammation or immune activation, nutrient allocation shifts away from growth toward maintenance and immune defense, which changes the effective energetic efficiency of the bird (Noblet et al., 2022). Under such conditions, the effective energy value of a diet may differ from that observed in healthy birds. This represents a major opportunity for future research and innovation: the next generation of NE systems could be linked to biomarkers of inflammatory status, gut integrity, and microbial functionality. Such integration would move NE beyond static feed evaluation toward a dynamic precision-nutrition platform supporting both productivity and robustness; a direction that is fully aligned with recent recommendations for the future development of broiler NE systems (Noblet, 2024).

Proposed industry roadmap

To move from concept to routine use, an industry roadmap should progress through sequential but overlapping steps: first, harmonization of calorimetry protocols and decision rules for NE determination; second, validation of prediction equations across broiler genotypes, ages, and ingredient matrices; third, comparative evaluation of ME- and NE-based least-cost formulation under commercial ingredient volatility; fourth, integration of NE into low-CP formulation strategies and feed additive screening programs; and finally, validation of business outcomes at the farm level using zootechnical, carcass, and economic indicators (Wu et al., 2019; Tay-Zar et al., 2024; Noblet, 2024).

Table 1: 6 steps for NE implementation.

Step	Priority area	Practical objective
1	1. Standardize measurement and prediction	Establish common internal protocols for calorimetry, bird age and genotype, adaptation periods, feed intake normalization, and equation selection. Without methodological discipline, NE datasets will not be comparable enough for routine deployment.
2	2. Build a practical ingredient database	Translate research NE values into a formulation-ready ingredient matrix covering major cereals, protein meals, fats, co-products, and alternative or novel ingredients. Systematically document both the source of values and the confidence level for each ingredient.
3	3. Pilot least-cost reformulation	Run parallel ME- and NE-based formulation exercises across broiler starter, grower, and finisher phases. Quantify impact on ingredient ranking, crude protein level, amino acid density, and shadow prices before any commercial launch decision.
4	4. Validate with performance and carcass responses	Confirm that reformulated diets maintain or improve growth, feed conversion, carcass composition, and margin over feed cost. Validation should include both controlled trials and selected field conditions.
5	5. Extend to technology evaluation	Use NE as an additional and complimentary response criterion for enzymes and other functional additives. This is particularly relevant where additive value is expressed through reduced heat increment, endogenous losses, or improved nutrient partitioning, rather than digestibility alone.
6	6. Connect NE to resilience metrics	In longer-term R&I programs, integrate NE with sanitary challenge models, inflammatory biomarkers, and health-related production losses. This will clarify whether the usable energy supply of feeds changes under non-ideal or stress conditions.

Conclusion

Net energy is increasingly positioned as the most biologically relevant energy system for poultry feeds and diets. (Noblet et al., 2022). Its value for industry lies in better ingredient ranking, more realistic economic formulation, improved interpretation of low-protein strategies, and potentially greater sensitivity to enzyme and health, and

resilience-oriented technologies (Wu et al., 2019; de Rauglaudre et al., 2023). Implementation should proceed in a pragmatic and stepwise manner: first through harmonized methodology and transparent, well validated prediction equations, then through pilot reformulation and benchmark exercises, and finally through commercial-scale validation linked to bird performance, carcass quality, economic return, and health-related indicators. In that sense, implementing NE is not merely a change in energy units but rather a strategic roadmap toward a more predictive and biologically aligned poultry nutrition system (Tay-Zar et al., 2024).

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17. Perspectives on the application of net energy systems in the US Poultry Industry

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Introduction

To apply the net energy system in the US Poultry Industry, reliable metabolizable energy (ME) values, with and without adjustment to nitrogen, net energy (NE) values, and their energetic equations are needed to build and gain confidence for the poultry nutritionist.

To determine the NE values of ingredients, the ME values of ingredients should be determined or calculated accurately in growing chickens. The NE values might be determined from protein and fat deposition, indirect calorimetric, or a new methodology proposed herein called calibration by feed conversion. This last technique might be applied if the NE determination of ingredient is not yet researched. The calibration methodology is based on feed conversion of practical diets using the particular ingredient.

After the NE is determined, the energetic efficiency, expressed as NE/ME, is also calculated for each ingredient. These energetic efficiencies should be utilized because these values are less variable as compared to their absolute NE values. When the NE/ME are found of each ingredient, these values are used directly in the formulation; or these values are applied to find-tune NE equations with proper adjustment as a starting point. A unique NE equation (Tayr-Zar et al., 2023) to be

applied for all ingredients is not suitable, several equations from other references might be the best options.

Finally, once energetic efficiencies of ingredients are found, these values should be applied for feed formulation using the same dietary NE values from corn-soybean meal-based diets. Using multiple feed ingredients, in addition of corn-soybean meal, reduces feed cost specially if NE/ME of ingredients is over 0.72.

Metabolizable energy values for feed ingredients

The best we know the metabolizable energy values of feed ingredients, the best we can determine or calculate the net energy values of feed ingredients, by using the energetic efficiency between net energy and ME ($NE/ME = K$). However, there are a few ME values of feed ingredients and more ME values adjusted to nitrogen (MEn) of feed ingredients. The MEn and the energy reduced by the adjustment of nitrogen is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Metabolizable energy values for feed ingredients.

Ingredients	AMEn ¹ , kcal/kg	n ²	SEM	[AME – AMEn],	n ²	SEM
	DM			kcal/kg DM		
Corn	3659	18	46.1	86	15	11.8
Wheat	3391	17	50.6	96	14	7.9
Sorghum	3543	12	50.1	86 ⁴		
Barley	3006	19	34.9	82	6	10.6
Wheat bran	2053	12	119.3	95	6	16
Palm meal	1960	8	156.6	56	4	4.4
Rice bran	2645	9	190.1	201	4	21.2
Soybean meal	2477	18	31.6	242	10	11.5
DDGS	2669	14	83.9	172	10	13.9
Soy full fat	3680	18	50.3	222	8	20.1
Corn gluten meal	3993	7	60.3	235	3	47.9
Poultry meal	3251	10	148.6	255	4	66.1
Meat and bone meal	2460	10	104.0	201	8	24.1
Fish meal	3078	8	90.7	227	2	68.7
Feather meal	2967	6	124.7	390	4	42.5
Corn oil	8823	5	110.9	121 ⁵		
Crude soybean oil	8584	8	99.9	121	7	25.0
Poultry fat	8481	4	87.0	121 ⁵		
Lard	8306	6	241.8	121 ⁵		
Palm oil	7323	5	426.2	125	3	58.8
Tallow	7320	10	186.8	121 ⁵		

¹Apparent metabolizable energy adjusted to nitrogen (AMEn). Apparent metabolizable energy (AME). SEM = standard error of the mean.

²n: number of studies run in broiler chickens.

³Dried distiller's grain with soluble = DDGS.

⁴Value assumed similar as corn.

⁵Value assumed similar as soybean oil.

The AME values of feed ingredients might calculated as the sum between MEn and the difference of [AME – AMEn], as follow:

$$\text{AME, kcal/kg asis} = \text{AMEn} \times \text{DM} + [\text{AME} - \text{AMEn}] \times \text{DM}; \text{Equation 1}$$

Then, the AMEn values of each ingredient are estimated from their proximal analysis, using their energy equations (Table 2). These energy equations were developed by Credinser LLC (2026) and then the ME values of each ingredients might be calculated as Equations 1.

Table 2. Calculated metabolizable energy values of feed ingredients¹.

Ingredients	DM	CP	EE	CF	Ash	NFE	NDF	AMEn ²	AME ³
Corn	86.5	8.2	2.18	1.2	1.2	73.7	10.6	3222	3297
Wheat	87.5	11.5	1.6	2.4	1.6	70.4	12.2	2976	3060
Sorghum	88.0	7.4	2.5	2.4	1.3	74.4	10.0	3233	3313
Barley	87.1	10.8	1.7	4.25	2.18	68.2	18.9	2618	2689
Wheat bran	88.5	15.1	3.4	9.1	4.4	56.5	39.6	1772	1854
Palm meal	93.9	17.0	5.9	15.0	4.3	51.7	66.6	1734	1786
Rice bran	88.3	13.4	15.1	7.7	7.6	44.5	22.2	2946	3123
Soybean meal	88.5	46.4	1.4	5.0	5.5	30.2	12.6	2322	2536
DDGS	89.0	27.5	8.8	7.3	4.7	40.8	29.6	2763	2916
Soy full fat	89.0	34.0	20.0	5.0	4.2	25.8	11.7	3705	3903
CGM	91.2	61.5	2.0	1.2	1.9	24.6	3.7	3642	3856
Poultry meal	94.0	53.0	14.0	2.5	19.0	5.5	0.0	3056	3296
MBM	94.0	49.3	10.7	2.5	27.0	4.5	0.0	2606	2794
Fish meal	93.5	62.5	6.7	0.0	21.0	3.3	0.0	2949	3137
Feather meal	91.8	83.1	4.7	0.0	2.7	1.3	0.0	2666	3024

¹Proximal analysis expressed as % and energy values as kcal/kg as is. DM = dry matter; CP = crude protein; EE = ether extract; CF = crude fiber; NFE = nitrogen free extract; NDF = nitrogen detergent fiber; AMEn = apparent metabolizable energy adjusted to nitrogen; AME = apparent metabolizable energy. CGM: corn gluten meal; DDGS: Dried distiller's grain with soluble; MBM = meat and bone meal.

²AMEn: corn: [123.26xCP+45.23xEE-4.39xCF+27.52xNFE]x1.0306; wheat: [123.26xCP+45.23xEE-4.39xCF+27.52xNFE]x1.0306; sorghum: [107.31xCP+186.34xCF+23.72xNFE]x1.0755; barley + enzyme: (-112.13xEnzymelo = Enzyme/1=no enzymel)+75.68xCP+97.40xEE+95.09xCF+17.90xNFE]x1.004; wheat bran: [43.90xCP- 70.38xCF + 30.93xNFE]; palm meal: [178.28xCP-216.8xCF+37.81xNFE]; rice bran: [-265.48xCP + 147.21xEE - 57.42xCF +105.82xNFE]; soybean meal: [40.99xCP + 19.89xEE + 35.78xCF + 6.25xNFE]x1.011; DDGS: (86.55xEE + 272.21xCF -18.84x[Level of inclusion of diet, 2.5%])x1.028; soy-full fat: [31.21xCP + 50.55xEE + 53.88xNFE +242.95x(Extruded=1, Toasted=0) - 117.64x(Mash=1, Pellet=0, from diets)]; corn gluten meal: 42.96xCP + 40.59xNFE; poultry meal: [41.44xCP + 83.21xEE - 22.66xAsh]x1.0427; meat and bone meal: 21.84xDM +7.24xCP + 21.79xEE -15.16x[Level of inclusion in diet, 2.5%]; fish meal: (26.32xDM +15.68xCP+30.33xEE - 47.04xAsh)x1.1106; feather meal: (39.25xCP +69.32xEE - 370.21xAsh)x1.0244.

³AME = AMEn + [AME - AMEn]xDM.

After knowing the AME of each ingredient, the net energy values are calculated from their energetic efficiencies (NE/AME). These energetic efficiencies are determined from their protein and fat deposition, indirect calorimetry, or calibration method. This last method is determined from the feed conversion in practical diets and providing the extra energy from this difference of feed conversion between the control and test ingredient, assuming 35 kcal per 1 point of feed conversion (0.01) and multiplied by 0.70 of energetic efficiency.

Determined energetic efficiencies (K) are used to calculate the NE values of each feed ingredients. These determined K values were also applied as reference to calculate and find the proper adjustment, above or below to one, of the net energy equations to mimic similar values (Table 3).

Table 3. Calculated net energy values of feed ingredients¹.

Ingredients	NE	K ²	Equations for net energy	References
Corn	2380	0.722	[29.49xCP+40.58xEE+28xNFE-40.14xCF]x1.016	Credinser, 2022
Wheat	2249	0.735	[29.49xCP+40.58xEE+28xNFE-40.14xCF]x0.986	Credinser, 2022
Sorghum	2512	0.758	[0.8737xAME-11.87xCP-13.5xEE-3.859xNFE+10.75xNDF]x0.995	Swick et al. 2013
Barley	1857	0.690	[0.8527xAME-3.81xCP-10.75xEE-3.99xNFE+2.21xCF]x0.942	Swick et al. 2013
Wheat bran	1275	0.688	[0.8527xAME-3.81xCP-10.75xEE-3.99xNFE+2.21xCF]x0.995	Swick et al. 2013
Palm meal	1117	0.625	[-6.21xCP + 4.782xEE-11.71xCF+0.767xAME]	Tay-Zar et al. 2024
Rice bran	2519	0.807	[-6.21xCP + 4.782xEE-11.71xCF+0.811xAME]x1.036	Tay-Zar et al. 2024
Soybean meal	1516	0.598	[-6.21xCP + 4.782xEE-11.71xCF+0.732xAME]	Tay-Zar et al. 2024
DDGS	1796	0.616	[0.7823xAME-4.649xCP-13.28xEE+11.93xCF]x0.846	Swick et al. 2013
Soy-full fat	2848	0.730	[0.8527xAME-3.81xCP-10.75xEE-3.99xNFE+2.21xCF]x0.985	Swick et al. 2013
CGM	2292	0.594	[0.8737xAME-11.87xCP-13.5xEE-3.859xNFE+10.75xNDF]x0.967	Swick et al. 2013
Poultry meal	2434	0.739	[29.49xCP+40.58xEE+28xNFE-40.14xCF]x1.114	Credinser, 2022
MBM	2258	0.808	[29.49xCP+40.58xEE+28xNFE-40.14xCF]x1.18	Credinser, 2022
Fish meal	1865	0.595	[0.8737xAME-11.87xCP-13.5xEE-3.859xNFE]x1.077	Swick et al. 2013
Feather meal	1505	0.498	[-6.21xCP + 4.782xEE-11.71xCF+0.661xAME]	Tay-Zar et al. 2024

¹Proximal analysis expressed as % and net energy values as kcal/kg as is. DM = dry matter; CP = crude protein; EE = ether extract; CF = crude fiber; NFE = nitrogen free extract; NDF = nitrogen detergent fiber; NE = net energy; AME = apparent metabolizable energy. CGM: corn gluten meal; DDGS: Dried distiller's grain with soluble; MBM = meat and bone meal.

²K = NE/AME values determined from literature and developed from Credinser. AME = AMEn + [AME - AMEn]xDM.

In the scenario that feed formulation is made using only net energy values of corn, soybean meal (SBM), and soy oil, no economic benefit is showed as changed from ME to NE system as target objective. In contrast, the additions of other feed ingredients such as meat and bone meal, poultry meal, soy-full fat, polishing rice, wheat, or sorghum reveal economic benefits in the NE system as compared to the ME system. This advantage is observed because the NE values of multiple ingredient diets has higher values than NE values from corn-SBM diets. Thus, the NE diets from multiple ingredients, except DDGS, needs to be reduced to have similar values of NE from corn-SBM diets. For instance, corn-SBM diet contains 2184 kcal/kg of NE and 3070 kcal/kg of AME, but if sorghum is included at 25% and formulated to 3070 kcal/kg of ME, the NE increases from 2184 to 2208 kcal/kg under the ME system formulation. Contrary, formulated under the NE system, the NE is decreased from 2208 to 2184 kcal/kg and the price is also reduced from 480.2 to 475.7 \$/MT.

Conclusion

The application of net energy diets requires information and confidence. Equations of ME or NE values for feed ingredients might be modified as you gain experiences based on in-vivo test. Formulations based on NE system gains economic advantages when wheat, sorghum, full-fat soybean meal, polishing rice, meat and bone meal, or poultry meal is incorporated in corn-soybean meal diets.

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18. Perspectives for implementing NE systems in the poultry industry in Brazil

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Introduction

Commercial poultry production has entered an era where efficiency of resource utilization becomes paramount to most broiler integrators. Ensuring that energetic efficiency is optimized will translate into adequate and efficient amounts of skeletal muscle protein and fat tissue deposition in broilers. Depending on the specific market conditions (e.g. live bird, breast meat yield, FCR), formulation of dietary energy and balanced protein can shift to optimize an economical return.

Through the years, several investigators have looked into delineating a Net Energy (NE) system for poultry (Hill and Anderson, 1958; Tay-Zar et al., 2023; Noblet et al., 2024; Martinez et al., 2025), but opportunities have been identified with regards to fiber content, protein-rich feed ingredients, and methodology, among others. Until a general consensus is reached by the scientific community, and matrices fine-tuned for all major feed ingredients, the industry is likely to resist adopting the new technology. But the question we must ask is: how much do we continue to “leave on the table” by refusing to experiment with this technology in current formulation and production systems?

In current times, it is natural to question the impact that politics play on global energy prices. Whether the crisis is happening in Russia/Ukraine or in the Strait of Hormuz, feed energy prices can often parallel those occurring with global energy.

Moving Forward

For the most part, there is a good understanding on how modern commercial broiler strain crosses respond to metabolizable energy (Farrell, 1974; Dale and Fuller, 1980; Dozier et al., 2007; Dozier et al., 2011), regardless of the source. If NE is obtained via heat dissipation quantification or by measuring gas consumption and production, the end result should be similar. Consequently, after quantifying this heat production, NE becomes simply an AME_n without heat production (not considering that from fasting), and its value is limited in what it can provide to the industry. Additional tangible benefits would be, in my opinion, categorizing the portion of energy destined for maintenance, and subsequently further categorize that destined for tissue deposition of fat or protein. The dairy industry has been able to categorize the energy destined for lactation, therefore it is reasonable to expect that when NE can finally be adopted it should be able to further refine the caloric portion needed for production, whether this is described in the form of gain for broilers, or oviposition as in the case of broiler breeders or commercial layers. For a recent comprehensive review that encompasses the various applications of energy in broiler production, please refer to Maharjan et al. 2021.

Conclusion

In spite of the considerable interest that this topic brings, consensus on how to obtain and describe NE does not appear to be happening anytime soon for poultry. Efforts have been made, and continue to be made, to characterize the most applicable form of NE, but until a reasonable agreement is not obtained by the scientific community, and until a few of integrators have tested the concept in their operations, it is unlikely that the industry will embrace this new technology that has the potential to dramatically improve resource utilization and enhance sustainability.

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19. Application of the Modelling Tool in Broiler Chicken Nutrition

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Introduction

Broiler nutrition now operates at the intersection of biological efficiency, economic pressure, and sustainability. Under these conditions, mechanistic models are useful as they integrate growth biology with feed, environment, and management, allowing users to test scenarios before implementation. The Broiler Growth Model (BGM), developed at Sao Paulo State University (UNESP), Jaboticabal, Brazil, is a web-based tool designed to predict feed intake, growth, body composition, and nutrient requirements of broilers under practical production conditions (Hauschild et al. 2015; Reis et al. 2023). Built on the feed intake concepts proposed by Emmans, the model assumes that birds attempt to consume enough feed to achieve their growth potential, while acknowledging that actual intake may be constrained by diet characteristics, environment, and other biological limitations (Emmans 1987).

The current BGM represents an important step in the evolution of nutritional modelling at UNESP. It is based on the AVINESP model (Hauschild et al., 2015), with new information on body composition, feed bulk constraints, carcass prediction, stochasticity, and optimization (Goncalves et al. 2020; Nascimento et al. 2020; Azevedo et al. 2021a, 2021b; Reis et al. 2023). Consequently, the software is relevant both in academia, for teaching systems thinking and evaluating nutritional hypotheses, and in industry, for feed program design, scenario testing, and target-oriented decisions.

The objective of this work is to provide an overview of the BGM, with emphasis on practical software navigation, simulation of growth and nutrient requirements, calibration of genetic potential, and optimization of feed programs.

Model architecture and practical workflow

The software is organized into three main modules: Basic Registration, Simulation, and Optimization. The Basic Registration module structures all the information required prior to running any simulation, including the definition of customers, ingredient databases, animal profiles, and environmental conditions. Within this module, users can also establish feeding strategies through diet composition and diet programs. In addition, the software incorporates a feed formulation tool based on Least-Cost Formulation principles, enabling the formulation of diets under defined ingredient and nutrient constraints and their direct evaluation within the growth model. The feed formulation tool allows nutrient constraints to be aligned with model outputs; for instance, previously saved simulations can be used to automatically populate nutritional targets for phase feeding, ensuring consistency between predicted requirements and formulated diets. As shown in Figure 1, this part of the workflow is where the biological and nutritional description of the system is assembled before decision-making begins.

Figure 1. Screenshot of the BGM main screen highlighting the three modules and the starting point for data registration.

Simulation, output interpretation, and calibration of genetic potential

The Simulation module integrates the previously registered customer, diet program, animal profile, environment, day-one weight, population size, flock condition, and optional health problems into a single run. Results are presented in plots and tables, which makes the software useful for both teaching and applied decision support. Because BGM is stochastic, it can simulate a population of birds, thereby allowing the user to evaluate not only expected means but also flock-level biological variation (Reis et al. 2023). At the mechanistic level, the model uses protein deposition as the driving force for growth and derives lipid, water, and ash deposition from allometric relationships. Desired intake is predicted from the first limiting resource, whereas actual intake may be constrained by feed bulk (Nascimento et al. 2020), heat loss, and maximum lipid deposition (Emmans, 1987).

A valuable feature for users aiming to realistically represent their production systems is the calibration of genetic potential. Because genetic selection continuously modifies the performance of commercial strains, default model parameters may gradually lose accuracy over time. In the BGM, the animal profile can be calibrated using a previously saved simulation together with observed live weight data collected over the production cycle. The software adjusts the predicted growth curve and returns updated parameters, which can then be saved as a new genotype. This functionality is relevant because the entire simulation framework is driven by the genetic potential of the animal; therefore, accurately defining this potential is essential to realistically mimic on-farm conditions. Figure 2 illustrates the calibration environment and how simulated growth outputs can be interpreted within this process.

Figure 2. Screenshot of the calibration tool, before (left) and after (right) adjust the genetic profile with observed body weight data.

Simulating a health-related issue

A key feature of the simulation module is the incorporation of health-related disturbances into flock predictions. In addition to nutritional, genetic, and environmental inputs, BGM includes two health scenarios. The first simulates coccidiosis, accounting for the reduction in feed intake associated with *Eimeria maxima* infection, which consequently leads to reduced growth, based on de Freitas et al. (2023). The second represents a general health condition, allowing users to mimic non-specific sanitary or management-related challenges that impair performance, even in the absence of a clearly defined disease. In this case, a health-status factor (1.0 to 0.8) is applied to reduce the flock's effective genetic potential, reflecting performance losses described in broilers under health challenges (Remus et al., 2014). Together, these features enable simulations under more realistic field conditions, enhancing the applicability of BGM for both academic evaluation and practical decision-making.

Optimization and application in academy and industry

The Optimization module moves the BGM from prediction to decision support. After a simulation is saved, the user can select digestible lysine, balanced protein, or metabolizable energy as the dietary component to be optimized, define minimum and maximum bounds for variation, and add economic values for live body weight, carcass, and cuts. The software then compares possible feeding programs and

returns the solution that maximizes economic return for each market endpoint. This is biologically important because the nutrient level that maximizes performance is not always the one that maximizes profitability (Gous 2015; Azevedo et al. 2021b). In the evaluation reported by Reis et al. (2023), BGM reproduced expected responses to protein and nutrient density, and the overall prediction error was up to 15% for feed intake, body weight, and body protein, supporting its use as a practical decision-support model.

In academia, these capabilities make BGM a valuable platform for hypothesis testing, teaching, and interpretation of nutrient-response experiments. In industry, the same framework can be used to compare feed programs, adapt nutrient density to a given objective, account for environmental and health-related constraints, and discuss the economic consequences of nutritional decisions before implementation in the field. Figure 3 represents an optimization interface and its profit-based output.

Figure 3. Screenshot of the optimization module showing the selection of the optimized dietary component and the economic output tabs.

Conclusion

The Broiler Growth Model is a mechanistic, web-based tool that connects growth theory with practical decision-making in broiler chicken nutrition. Its value lies not only in estimating feed intake, growth, body composition, and nutrient requirements, but also in linking these predictions to calibration of genetic potential and to economic optimization of feeding programs. A demonstration is given to show how BGM can be used as a bridge between academic modelling and applied nutrition, helping users

interpret biological limits, formulate better feeding strategies, and select scenarios that are technically sound and economically relevant.

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Synopsis

Current precision nutrition practices in poultry require tools that help nutritionists, researchers, and poultry science professionals adopt strategies to optimize resource utilization in nutrition and feeding. Modeling is a powerful tool that, through mathematical functions adapted to practical computational programs, supports nutritionists in making efficient, real-time decisions and enables fast, easy application under dynamic scenarios. Additionally, the net energy system is presented as a novel system that, upon implementation, can help not only generate energy but also improve nutrient utilization. Both topics require a metabolic understanding of birds under different scenarios to accurately determine requirements and feed value. As a complementary topic, this book presents an overview discussion of the application of modeling and advances in net energy systems for poultry, aiming to implement these technologies in practical feed formulation for sustainable and efficient poultry production.

This book collects papers presented at the Symposium on Nutritional Modeling and Energy Metabolism in Poultry Nutrition 2026, bringing together the best and most recent academic-practical discussions from international researchers.

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